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OFFSHORE CCS MMV

State of the Art

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Carbon Capture and Storage

Carbon emissions are one of the most well-documented and researched contributors to climate change (Jones et al., 2023). Carbon dioxide (CO₂), essential to life, has become problematic due to its high concentrations in the atmosphere and oceans. The consequences of these elevated levels are evident: global warming (e.g. Jones et al., 2023), extreme weather events (Yang et al., 2021; Van Aalst, 2006), ocean acidification (Turley, 2013; Parker et al., 2013), the degradation of cultural heritage through acid rain in urban centres (Rodríguez et al., 2023; Camuffo, 1992), and increased health risks from deteriorating outdoor air quality (Tran et al., 2023). Each of these outcomes highlights the urgency of reducing carbon emissions, as agreed in 2015 at the 21st session of the Conference of Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). As part of the efforts to reach net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2040-2050, a global coalition of scientists, investors, public organisations, and industries have been collaborating to develop Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies. Preliminary findings suggest that along with many other solutions that need to be implemented, CCS holds considerable promise in reducing CO₂ emissions, particularly by dealing with industries where emissions are currently hard to eliminate, and demonstrates positive initial results (Waarum et al., 2017).

CCS is a technology designed to reduce carbon emissions from major industrial sources, including cement, iron, and steel production, which together account for approximately 13.5% of global CO₂ emissions (C2ES, 2024; Fennell et al., 2022). The process is represented illustratively in Figure 1. It starts by capturing CO₂ from emitter sources, typically using chemical solvents like amines (Enbridge, 2024; Osman et al., 2020). Amines selectively absorb CO₂ from flue gases, enabling its separation from other gases. Once isolated, the CO₂ is pressured into a dense liquid state, facilitating its transport and further storage (Enbridge, 2024; Osman et al., 2020).

After pressurisation, the CO₂ is transported, most often through pipelines but also via rail or ship when pipelines are impractical (Enbridge, 2024). Once it reaches the storage site, typically a depleted oil or gas reservoir or a saline aquifer, the CO₂ is injected into porous rock formations at depths of over 800 metres and under layers of impermeable rock known as caprock (Jones & Lawson, 2022; GCCSI, 2016). This geological cap provides a natural seal, preventing the CO₂ from escaping and ensuring long-term containment (GCCSI, 2016).

Figure 1 - Illustration of the different phases of the CCS process, from capture to storage. CO₂ can be also used for enhanced oil recovery and in the production of fertilisers, CO₂-based synthetic fuels and other chemicals. In this case the acronym CCUS (Carbon capture, utilization and storage) is often used. From VectorMine (2021), Carbon capture process with compression and transport for utilization outline concept (Vector illustration), Adobe Stock. URL: <https://stock.adobe.com/images/carbon-capture-process-with-compression-and-transport-for-utilization-outline-concept-labeled-educational-steps-and-stages-explanation-for-co2-reduction-and-storage-principle-vector-illustration/474909745>

Despite their effectiveness, CCS systems remain in a relatively nascent stage, requiring significant investment, intensive research, and technical expertise (GCCSI, 2024a). They also carry inherent risks in implementation. CCS projects have been executed for various purposes, such as Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) and climate change mitigation, with the first representing their primary application (Holloway et al., 2007; Jenkins, 2020). By 2022, there were 196 CCS projects in development globally (GCCSI, 2022). Two years later, the outcome has expanded significantly, with 50 CCS projects fully operational, 44 under construction, and a total of 628 projects at various stages in the CCS facilities pipeline (GCCSI, 2024a). These projects collectively aim for a capture capacity of 416 million tonnes per annum (Mtpa), with the majority located onshore. However, offshore CCS projects are growing significantly as infrastructure and technology in this area are also available (GCCSI, 2024a).

In Europe, as of July 2024, there are 191 commercial CCS projects either operational or progressing through development stages. Among these, 23 fully operational projects target deep saline formations (greenfield sites), while 18 focus on depleted oil and gas fields

(brownfield sites), aiming to leverage existing infrastructure to reduce costs and environmental impact (GCCSI, 2024; Wolaver et al., 2013).

While a substantial number of projects exist, societal acceptance of CCS technology remains limited (Nielsen et al., 2022). Consequently, Measurement, Monitoring, and Verification (MMV) became a primary research focus, as enhanced monitoring capabilities can foster greater public trust in CCS projects. Improving MMV plans, and having a transparent behaviour before society, will ensure safety, environmental protection, and compliance with regulatory frameworks (Waarum et al., 2017).

This work aims to characterise the current state of MMV practices in offshore CCS projects. The focus on offshore projects relates with the storage site (greenfield saline aquifer) that was identified by the University of Évora together with other partners to implement the Portuguese emission reduction targets towards carbon neutrality by 2045. To achieve this goal, a comprehensive review of previous state-of-the-art studies (Jenkins, 2020; Hannis et al., 2015) was conducted alongside an examination of numerous public reports from research organisations and industry leaders, such as [Global CCS Institute, IEA, USED, IEAGHG]. The focus was on identifying preferred MMV techniques, applications, advancements, and limitations within the field. For optimal comprehension and to gain deeper insight into specific concepts and techniques discussed, readers are encouraged to consult the articles cited throughout this document. As a complement and support it is recommended the consultation of Appendix 1 which contains different tables summarising the various monitoring techniques (DNV, 2024).

Monitoring in offshore CCS projects (MMV - Measurement, Monitoring, and Verification)

As previously mentioned, monitoring of CCS sites has evolved considerably, driven by the need to ensure secure containment of CO₂ within sub-seabed formations and long-term stability of storage systems. However, the absence of systematic documentation or established standards and guidelines for detecting and monitoring leaks can present challenges in the design phase of subsea leakage detection systems (Waarum et al., 2017). Hence, it is necessary to document, establish, and standardise methodologies, in order to achieve a properly working system. At first, it is important to clarify some basic concepts and regulations that should frame the MMV. For a better understanding of the subject, this section will focus on the summary and analysis of three main documents published by IEAGHG (2015), Waarum et al. (2017) and Jenkins (2020). This section will introduce the most relevant offshore CCS monitoring concepts, highlighting the maturity level of technologies and methodologies as well as of regulations.

In CCS, as presented by Wolaver et al. (2013), we can distinguish “Brownsites” and “Greensites”, where Brownsites can be defined as “volumes that have had previous deep-subsurface industrial use” and Greensites as volumes that “lack subsurface development”. Thus, Brownsites are always Brownfields (e.g.: depleted oil and gas fields) whereas Greensites include Brownfields with “limited or no industrial subsurface activity” or “a relatively undeveloped surface and subsurface” – the motivation behind this differentiation focuses on the characterisation, risk, and monitoring needs that come with the geologic setting as well as the established regulatory framework.

Offshore CO₂ storage is governed by key international agreements such as the **London Protocol** and the **OSPAR Convention**, which establish two-stage monitoring frameworks focusing on CO₂ containment within storage formations and environmental impact assessment in the event of leakage. The former is an international agreement aimed at safeguarding the marine environment by controlling the disposal of waste into the sea. While Europe has the most developed regulatory framework, similar regulations have emerged and are evolving in countries like **Japan, Australia, and the United States**, all emphasising the importance of monitoring to ensure storage site safety, effectiveness, and future conformance. In Europe, regulation-wise, monitoring relies on the **European CO₂ Storage Directive** and the **OSPAR Guidelines**. The European CO₂ Storage Directive, introduced in 2007, essentially provides a regulatory framework for the permanent storage of CO₂ in quantities exceeding 100kt, which

requires operators to monitor injection facilities, the storage complex (including, when feasible, the CO₂ plume), and, where appropriate, the surrounding environment for the following four purposes (IEAGHG, 2015; Waarum et al., 2017; Jenkins, 2020):

- Assessing whether injected CO₂ is behaving as expected;
- Detecting any migration or leakage of CO₂;
- Evaluation of significant adverse effects on the environment or Human health;
- Assessing the effectiveness of corrective measures.

The directive also mandates that monitoring activities must be based on a monitoring plan that is updated throughout the project's lifecycle as the risk profile evolves and incorporates advancements in scientific knowledge and the best available technology.

On the other hand, the OSPAR Guidelines for Risk Assessment and Management of CO₂ Storage in Geological Formations are focused on the protection of the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic. The Guidelines emphasise the need for monitoring across all phases of a CO₂ storage project, from baseline data collection to long-term post-injection monitoring and provide a framework to ensure that CO₂ storage does not lead to significant adverse consequences for the marine environment, Human health, or other legitimate uses of the maritime area (OSPAR Commission, 2007; IEAGHG, 2015).

OSPAR Guidelines also specify some of the main monitoring and control elements in order to achieve their objectives, such as:

- Injection rate;
- Continuous pressure monitoring;
- Injectivity and pressure fall-off testing;
- Properties of the injected fluid (including temperature, solid content, presence of incidental associated substances, and the phase of CO₂ flow);
- Mechanical integrity of caprock and wells (including abandoned wells);
- Containment of CO₂ flow, including performance monitoring and oversight of overlying formations to detect leakage;
- Control measures, overpressure monitoring, and emergency shutdown systems.

Monitoring, one of the most important steps of CCS safety, must be supported by a monitoring plan, which mandatorily has to detail the activities to be implemented during key project phases,

including baseline, operational, closure, and post-closure stages. For each phase, the plan should include the following:

- Monitored parameters;
- Employed monitoring technologies and the reasoning for their use;
- Monitoring locations and the rationale for spatial sampling;
- Frequency of monitoring and the rationale for temporal sampling.

Additionally, there are some requirements which the European Directive finds important, a range of continuous or intermittent monitoring activities, that may dictate project success, such as:

- Fugitive emissions at the injection facility;
- Volumetric CO₂ flow at injection wellheads;
- Injection pressure and temperature at injection wellheads;
- Chemical analysis of the injected material;
- Reservoir temperature and pressure.

The directive provides general guidance on monitoring technologies and their specific purposes. It also underscores that, following the closure of a storage site, the operator retains responsibility for monitoring until a post-closure plan has been submitted and approved by the Competent Authority. Approval of the post-closure plan requires clear evidence demonstrating that the stored CO₂ will remain securely and permanently contained. Monitoring activities may be scaled down to a level sufficient for detecting leaks or significant irregularities. However, if such events are identified, monitoring must be intensified as necessary to evaluate the extent of the issue and the effectiveness of corrective measures. Additionally, both regulations emphasise the critical importance of establishing spatial and temporal baseline conditions prior to the commencement of CO₂ injection. The baseline characterisation is fundamental for differentiating between natural variations and changes resulting from CO₂ storage. The choice of monitoring methods should be guided by the specific characteristics of the storage site and the potential risks associated with the project. A vital aspect of monitoring is the capacity to detect and quantify CO₂ emissions, which is particularly significant for projects operating under the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (IEAGHG, 2015; Jenkins, 2020).

Based on the regulatory frameworks it is possible to distinguish two main requirements in CCS monitoring that must be met to achieve efficiency and compliance, which creates a two-pronged approach preventing the CO₂ from escaping and making sure it behaves accordingly:

- **Containment** assures that CO₂ stays inside the designated storage site and does not leak;
- **Conformance** is making sure that the injected CO₂ stays within the established boundaries, thus, granting that it behaves as predicted.

This leads to the monitoring methods and technologies, which may focus on different depths (shallow or deep) and/or applications. While there are some distinctions between their objectives—such as ensuring containment or verifying conformance—they are ultimately quite similar in practice (Waarum et al., 2017). Multiple CCS projects have proven that a solid monitoring plan assures the success of the project and to build the monitoring plan, we have to address the different strategies for offshore CCS monitoring. The probability of leakage is considerably low (Blomberg et al., 2021), so it is neither practical nor cost-effective to conduct detailed monitoring across the entire area for long periods. From previous experiences, an effective approach combines broad, low-intensity mapping in regions without identified risks with more focused and intensive monitoring in high-risk areas, such as near infrastructure, natural migration pathways, or in response to observed anomalies, like discrepancies between models and measurements.

From projects like Tomakomai (Goto et al., 2019; IEAGHG, 2015) in Japan, it was possible to infer the importance of establishing a strong baseline/background knowledge, also known as site characterisation, before CO₂'s injection. Understanding the marine environment and its variability is key to identify CO₂ leakage as well as identify its nature, natural or anthropogenic. Models, which can be used to predict environmental impacts, normally simulate hypothetical case scenarios where there is an immediate leakage of CO₂ followed by a slow migration along geological structures, which usually would take years. Given the complexity of these systems, detecting and characterising sites mandate a solid site-specific risk assessment in order to assure leak prevention.

To conduct the site-specific risk assessment, monitoring should be focused where it is most needed. Particularly, the identification of either natural or anthropogenic structures, such as fractures, faults, or legacy wells, will be crucial to assess environmental impact and prevent possible events.

Risk analysis is a cyclic process. Hence, with time, multiple revisions of the risk level should be done, and depending on site characteristics, it may or may not be more recurrent. Bowtie method, based on the barrier approach to risk assessment, provides a base framework for systematic risk assessment, including identifying risks and proposing proportional monitoring efforts. Blomberg et al. (2021) presented a simple yet representative risk-based approach, presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Cyclic behaviour of a risk-based CCS monitoring methodology (Blomberg et al., 2021).

In the same line of thought, DNV (2024), presents a similar representation for continuous MMV plans. However, in addition, they highlight modelling and mitigation actions, as illustrated in Figure 3.

As stated, the marine monitoring program should be site-specific, adapting to risk levels based on site conditions and anomalies. Key factors influencing the strategy include infrastructure, water depth, ocean currents, and overburden characteristics. Shallow risk structures may require geochemical monitoring for leakage precursors, while the number and condition of wells impact the need for detailed monitoring. These and other factors will be tackled and discussed, along the techniques deployed to study and monitor them, in the following section.

Figure 3 - Dynamic process of risk management that involves the ongoing collection of data, updating of predictive models, and the application of corrective or mitigating measures (DNV, 2024).

Overview of Techniques

1. Techniques for deep monitoring

1.1 Seismic Imaging

As Jenkins (2020) stated, the initial deployment of offshore CCS monitoring technologies was notably exemplified by projects such as Norway's Sleipner and Snøhvit in the North Sea and Barents Sea, respectively. As early as 1996, Sleipner set the benchmark for offshore monitoring with the application of time-lapse seismic surveys, achieving a remarkable cost of 2€ per Mt (Million ton) of CO₂ stored. This approach became crucial to visualise CO₂ plume evolution, providing the distribution of CO₂ within subsurface reservoirs (IEAGHG, 2015). The success of Sleipner established seismic as the foundational technique, affirming its reliability in detecting and tracking the CO₂ plume, and thus setting a precedent for subsequent offshore CCS projects. Seismic methods provide potentially high-resolution imaging and characterisation of the subsurface of wide areas, namely the detection of changes in the fluid distribution and pressure in the reservoir (IEAGHG, 2015). In Figure 4, we can see some time-lapse seismic images of the Sleipner CO₂ plume as well as its evolution from the baseline in 1994 to 2010.

Surface seismic methods will rather see their best application in shallow, thick and unconsolidated reservoirs than in thin, deep lithified ones (Lumley et al., 1997). Thus, they are best suited for aquifer storage given the different seismic properties of dense-phase CO₂ and the reservoir brine. These surface seismic imaging tools allow a robust and uniform spatial surveillance of the storage complex for a long time as well as a very powerful leakage monitoring tool, since it can detect small changes in the fluid content in the reservoir and upper layers. When combined with its capability to track the CO₂ plume, it may assure that it is behaving accordingly with the predictions and respecting the regulatory frameworks.

Although these techniques have proven their utility and potential, they are only useful in very shallow scenarios, restricting their appliance/deployment. Since in most of CCS scenarios the reservoir is located at depths of 700m or more, these techniques end up losing their interest.

Figure 4 - A series of time-lapse seismic images of the Sleipner CO₂ plume illustrates its progression from the 1994 baseline to 2010. The top row displays changes in reflectivity along a north–south vertical section (inline). The middle row presents the evolution of reflectivity across the entire plume in a map view. The bottom row highlights changes in the topmost CO₂ layer using reflectivity difference maps (Jenkins et al., 2015)

While incredibly powerful and necessary, given the key importance of having robust overburden monitoring in every storage site scenario, seismic surveys also face some challenges in recovering valuable, reliable and precise data. Precise and trustworthy results require repeatability, so there is a need to use the same survey lines and equipment each time data is collected. Additionally, there are some other challenges and limitations that come with seismic imaging, such as:

- High costs;
- Resolution and Depth limitations;

- Environmental and Signal Interference;
- Data Processing and Interpretation Challenges;
- Health, Safety, and Environmental Risks;
- Economical and Societal impacts.

In recent years (DNV, 2024) researchers have made continuous efforts to refine monitoring techniques and develop advanced algorithms capable of generating increasingly accurate and detailed images of the CO₂ plume in the reservoir. These advancements aim to filter out background noise and isolate the signal of the CO₂ plume, enabling the detection of CO₂ accumulations as small as possible. This evolution, when combined with its time-lapse capability of tracking changes in 3D with time (4D seismic) and size adaptations (Mini-Streamers), enhance seismic imaging as an even more appealing MMV methodology, as will be discussed below.

1.2 Other Seismic Tools

1.2.1 Chirps, boomers, and pingers

High-resolution surface seismic techniques can be employed in time-lapse mode to detect seabed changes resulting from CO₂ leakage, granting their role in assuring containment. Under favourable conditions, they may also enable the direct detection of bubble streams in the water column. These systems operate at a range of frequencies, which cause free gas bubbles to resonate and scatter the signal, making them particularly effective for imaging purposes.

High-resolution single-channel seismic systems, operating within the frequency range of 2–10kHz, are commonly known as sub-bottom profilers (SBPs). These systems, sometimes referred to as shallow seismic sensors, are designed to generate real-time, high-resolution seismic reflection profiles of the seafloor and the upper metres of sediments (from 5 to 100m depending on sediment properties; Blomber et al., 2021). Typically, an SBP system comprises a transceiver unit, a transducer array (except in boomer systems), and a recording unit (Dondurur, 2018). There are four main types of SBP systems, in this case we will focus on 3 of them, single-frequency (Pingers), Chirps that use sweep frequencies and Boomers that use mechanical metal plates. These systems see their usefulness for storage site CO₂ monitoring in detecting seabed changes and potential leakage pathways. Chirps use broad frequency sweeps (2–13kHz) for shallow subsurface imaging with high resolution but are limited to depths of 30–40m. Pingers, operating at narrower frequencies (3.5–7kHz) and depths (~20m), are simpler and less expensive

but offer lower resolution. Boomers utilise mechanical energy to penetrate deeper (up to 60m) and identify faults and fractures, albeit at slower speeds compared to Chirps. These systems, deployable via AUVs or ROVs, provide versatile 2D imaging solutions but lack 3D coverage, limiting their effectiveness in many CCS scenarios. Additionally, these systems are very limited by depth since their utility is restricted to very shallow situations, thus they lose their interest as a monitoring tool for most CCS projects (Bull et al., 1998; Shin et al., 2022a Dondurur, 2018; Nasif, 2024).

1.3 OBS, OBN, & OBC. Ocean Bottom Seismometers, Nodes & Cables (OBC)

Ocean bottom recording has been in use for approximately 70 years, evolving significantly over time and becoming a well-studied and mature technology. The term Ocean Bottom Seismometers (OBS) refers to systems primarily employed by academic institutions and research organisations for monitoring micro-seismic activity and earthquakes

Additionally, they are utilised in long-offset refraction studies to assess deep strata, detect basement structures, and perform seismic tomography (Jack, 2021).

1.3.1 Ocean Bottom Cables (OBCs)

Detectors integrated into cable systems have been used in the seismic industry for many years, although their usage has become less common in recent times. These systems are deployed and retrieved using a mother ship, but the process is time-intensive, costly, and typically 7–8 times more expensive than conventional towed cable surveys (Jack, 2021).

Challenges increase with water depth due to ocean currents, which complicate operations and cause wear on cables. Poor coupling between detectors and the seabed can occur, especially in uneven terrain, where sensors may be suspended without seabed contact. Ocean currents can also generate noise through cable strumming, while wave noise may affect both OBC and OBN systems. Earlier OBC geophone units addressed alignment issues using gimbal mounts to ensure accurate vertical positioning of the z geophone. However, due to their inherent transfer function, it can introduce noise or distortions to seismic signals. As a result, it has become preferable to eliminate their use by orienting geophones based on first arrivals or employing MEMS accelerometer sensors capable of detecting vertical motion (Jack, 2021).

Seabed detectors, which may consist of a hydrophone combined with vertical motion detection or three-component motion sensing, transmit collected data through cables to the

recording equipment aboard the mothership. In terms of usage, Ocean Bottom Cable (OBC) systems have largely been surpassed by Ocean Bottom Node (OBN) systems, though they still play a role in specific applications such as Permanent Reservoir Monitoring (PRM) systems, which will be further explored (IEAGHG, 2015). Figure 5 illustrates a OBC system.

Figure 5 - Illustration of OBC system with data collection on a vessel. From Peakseismic (2024), Ocean Bottom Seismic (illustration), URL: <https://www.peakseismic.com/content/ocean-bottom-seismic.asp>

1.3.2 Ocean Bottom Nodes (OBNs)

Ocean Bottom Nodes (OBNs) and Ocean Bottom Seismometers (OBSs) are autonomous systems placed on the seabed to record seismic data, which is later retrieved for analysis. While both serve similar purposes, the term OBN is now preferred for reservoir-related seismic applications. OBNs present a cost-benefit solution, even more when combined with cheaper and versatile strategies or technologies such as AUVs (DNV, 2024). These seabed systems, particularly permanent seabed arrays, offer several advantages over conventional streamer seismics. They provide full-azimuth datasets and multicomponent sensors capable of p-wave and s-wave recording, supporting geomechanical and isotropy characterisation, fracture detection, and related analyses (Jack, 2021). These systems can also function in passive mode for extended monitoring of natural and induced seismicity as well as ambient noise, delivering data suitable for applications such as seismic interferometry (Jack, 2021). These tools grant their spotlight in containment and conformance due to their high-precision time-shift mapping that improves the detection of pressure changes within reservoirs and/or geomechanical variations in the overburden, enhanced by the repeatability achieved in time-lapse mode (Jack, 2021). Figure 6, illustrates the deployment of ocean bottom nodes from a surface vessel and using ROVs.

Figure 6 - Deployment of OBNs from a vessel by ROVs. From GeoExPro (2021), Ocean Bottom Seismic: Robots on the Seabed, URL: <https://geoexpro.com/ocean-bottom-seismic-robots-on-the-seabed/>

Since 2000, advancements in low-power electronics, larger-capacity batteries, enhanced deployment/recovery methods, and improved electronic data storage have significantly modernised OBN systems. These improvements have made them popular for 3D marine seismic surveys, where nodes remain operational for up to a month (Jack, 2021).

Despite high costs (\$35k–\$200k per km², with lower costs for depths up to 400 m using automation), OBN surveys are increasingly favoured due to their effectiveness (Jack, 2021). Costs are declining, and further reductions are expected as deployment innovations and blended source techniques become standard. By 2025, unit costs are projected to halve compared to 2015 levels (Jack, 2021; IEAGHG, 2015). The current priority is optimising operations to enhance spatial sampling while reducing survey costs. In an article published by Worldexpro (2019) it is pointed out that by 2019, the price of OBNs had decreased by about 45%, lining up with previous predictions (Jack, 2021).

OBCs and OBNs are both technologies that have been studied for a long time and recently have been targeted as potential standards within offshore CCS monitoring, namely due to PRMs. Since the last report issued by the IEA Greenhouse Gas R&D Programme, many projects have deployed this technology offshore, such as Sleipner, Snøhvit, and the Northern Lights, while achieving great cost cuts (IEAGHG, 2015; Worldexpro, 2019).

1.4 Seabottom Gravimetry

In saline aquifer CO₂ storage, dense-phase CO₂ has a significantly lower density than typical reservoir brine. Therefore, the injection of CO₂ creates a gravitational signal corresponding to the mass difference between the CO₂ plume and an equivalent volume of formation water (IEAGHG, 2015). This signal, measured in miliGals (mGals) or microGals (μGal), provides critical insights into subsurface changes. For optimal precision, gravimeters must be deployed on the seabed rather than acquiring data from a ship. Nowadays, gravimeters have been also attached to AUVs or ROVs.

Gravimetry presents a cost-effective, user-friendly, highly-sensitive, and accurate alternative to seismic methods and can also be integrated with geodetic approaches (Huang & Yang, 2021). Among geophysical monitoring techniques, gravimetry is particularly effective in detecting mass balance variations, namely resulting from CO₂ dissolution and CO₂ plume migration. However, gravimetry requires highly precise instrumentation, advanced data processing and modelling methods to overcome its inherent challenges, such as low resolution and stability (Biegert et al., 2008).

Nonetheless, gravimetry should be seen as a complementary monitoring tool, since it primarily measures mass changes within the reservoir, which relate to conformance parameters. When applied over time, gravimetry can track changes such as CO₂ plume migration, detect potential leakage due to mass movement into overburden formations, caprock integrity, and monitor overall reservoir integrity (IEAGHG, 2015). Gravimetry has been widely used and very well documented through projects like Sleipner, Snøhvit, and the Northern Lights Project (Nooner et al., 2007; IEAGHG, 2015).

1.5 Controlled Source Electromagnetics (CSEM)

Similarly to gravimetry, electromagnetic (EM) methods offer the potential for storage site monitoring. EM techniques deploy a time-variant source electrical field to induce secondary electrical and magnetic fields that carry information about the subsurface electrical structure (Macgregor, 2021). It is important to emphasise that electromagnetic (EM) methods measure resistivity, not hydrocarbons or any other specific substances directly. The resistivity of Earth materials spans several orders of magnitude. A key observation is that substituting conductive pore fluids with resistive hydrocarbons or a CO₂ plume can cause a significant increase in resistivity, often by an order of magnitude or more (MacGregor, 2021). This resistivity change is

the primary target for many marine EM surveys conducted over potential hydrocarbon-bearing prospects.

Therefore, resistivity data must be carefully interpreted in conjunction with seismic data and other information. A well calibrated rock physics framework grants an accurate assessment of the underlying rock and fluid properties (MacGregor, 2021).

Marine EM methods can be classified into two main categories: natural source (MT) and controlled source (CSEM) methods.

Natural source methods rely on electromagnetic fields naturally generated in the Earth's atmosphere and ionosphere as their source. In contrast, controlled source methods use artificially generated electromagnetic fields, which are produced by a source controlled and operated by the survey geophysicist, offshore CCS wise CSEM is the method that matters the most.

Controlled Source Electromagnetic (CSEM) is a geophysical method that utilises artificially generated electromagnetic fields to induce responses in the subsurface and map it (Alumbaugh et al., 2024; MacGregor, 2021). These responses are then detected and recorded by electric and/or magnetic field receivers, which are either deployed on the seafloor or towed behind the source. In industry applications, the use of electric dipole–dipole systems predominate (MacGregor, 2021). In these systems, both the source and the receiver are configured as electric dipoles. Currently, three main approaches are commonly employed, which Macgregor (2021) deeply distinguishes meticulously:

- Conventional Nodal HED–HED Methods
- Towed Streamer CSEM
- Vertical Electric Dipole Methods (VED – VED CSEM)

Overall, like gravimetry, electromagnetic (EM) methods can provide valuable complementary information to seismic surveys. They are particularly effective in detecting fluid saturation changes at higher CO₂ saturation levels, where seismic methods often lose sensitivity. However, EM methods come with significant logistical challenges. They require a source vessel as well as a seabed sensor array, which is complex to deploy. Additionally, EM methods are less effective in shallow water and are costly to implement, since their expenses are roughly comparable to those of offshore 3D seismic surveys (MacGregor, 2021).

The Sleipner project implemented this methodology and achieved data quality that was reportedly good (MacGregor, 2021). However, it identified shallow heterogeneities linked to artificial structures placed on the seafloor above the CO₂ plume. These structures generated artefacts that interfered with the CO₂ plume response. The artefacts were characterised by high spatial frequency, in contrast to the CO₂ signature, which displayed a broader spatial extent (IEAGHG, 2015). Figure 7 illustrates a 2D profile recorded along the long axis of the CO₂ plume as well as a comparison of the normalised data with a synthetic model built based on the logging data and lateral plume extent.

Figure 7 – a) 2D profile along the axis of the CO₂ plume; b) Comparison on amplitude (top) and phase (bottom) between field data and synthetic normalised by baseline data (IEAGHG, 2015).

1.6 Downhole Measurements

Downhole pressure and temperature measurements play a vital role in carbon capture and storage (CCS) operations by providing data that informs about reservoir conditions.

1.6.1 Pressure:

Pressure gauges continuously monitor reservoir pressure and detect any variations during the injection process (IEAGHG, 2015). These measurements are critical for evaluating pressure conditions within the storage reservoir and tracking CO₂ dynamics. By integrating data

from both surface and downhole pressure sensors, operators can effectively monitor the injection process, identify potential issues such as pressure build-up or leakage, and ensure operational safety. Designed to withstand the extreme high-pressure and high-temperature environments typical of downhole operations, these sensors are available in two configurations: conventional copper wire conduits for surface connectivity or advanced fibre optic systems (DNV, 2024).

1.6.2 Temperature:

Similarly, temperature sensors measure the temperature of the injected CO₂ as it enters the storage formation. These measurements provide valuable insights into phase behaviour within the well and at the entrance of the reservoir, helping in the prediction of and mitigation for hydrate formation (DNV, 2024). During pauses in injection, temperature data also reveal reservoir conditions, offering a broad understanding of the storage environment. When combined with surface data, downhole pressure and temperature readings enable operators to optimise the injection process and maintain storage efficiency (DNV, 2024).

To ensure maximum accuracy, downhole gauges are typically installed at or near the reservoir level. This placement is crucial as the density of CO₂ in the wellbore can vary significantly under different pressure and temperature conditions. For example, the Sleipner case highlighted the inadequacy of wellhead pressure measurements for determining reservoir pressure due to the two-phase behaviour of CO₂ in the wellbore (IEAGHG, 2015). These gauges can either be connected to the surface for continuous real-time data collection or deployed as retrievable memory gauges for periodic monitoring. Downhole pressure serves as a key conformance tool and plays a vital role in containment monitoring. Moreover, monitoring downhole conditions is a regulatory requirement in many jurisdictions, ensuring compliance and enhancing operational safety (Jenkins, 2020). Figure 8 shows the different measurements at Snhøvit from April 2008 to April 2009.

Figure 8 – Snhøvit’s in-hole pressure and temperature measurements. Legend reads: downhole pressure (pink) – QInl (km/hr), wellhead pressure (pale blue) – WHP (bar), temperature (yellow) – BHT (°C), and CO₂ injection rate (dark blue) – BHP (Bar), left axis reads “QInl, WHP & BHT (@gauge)”, right axis reads “BHP (@gauge – light blue line)” (IEAGHG, 2015).

By providing crucial insights into subsurface conditions, downhole pressure and temperature monitoring systems are indispensable for the safe, efficient, and effective operation of CCS projects. These tools not only support injection optimisation but also ensure the long-term monitoring of the integrity and safety of storage sites.

1.7 Logging

Geophysical logs are commonly collected in open (uncased) wellbores to analyse a broad range of *in situ* formation and fluid properties. Most techniques are standard oilfield practice, but interpretation has been modified for calculating CO₂ saturation (IEAGHG, 2015). For monitoring CO₂-related changes in a borehole, repeat logging becomes necessary after the well is cased (“cased-hole”), allowing formation measurements to be conducted through the casing and cement. Offshore applications face challenges due to the limited access to wells for repeat logging. Dedicated monitoring wells can be expensive and may not always justify the cost compared to the value of the data obtained. In such cases, access to injection or production wells for logging may be feasible during routine maintenance operations (DNV, 2024).

Numerous tools are available for time-lapse petrophysical monitoring, which can track the migration of injected CO₂ within the reservoir, such as (DNV, 2024; Elsayed et al., 2022; Nooner et al., 2007):

- **Time-Lapse Pulsed Neutron Logging (PNL) or saturation logging:** measures changes in fluid saturations over time;
- **Time-Lapse Neutron Logging:** monitors changes in neutron capture characteristics;
- **Time-Lapse Resistivity or Induction Logging (cased-hole):** ideal for detecting variations in resistivity due to fluid displacement;
- **Production Logging Tools (PLT):** combined with time-lapse temperature logging to evaluate changes in production and temperature profiles
- **Time-Lapse Sonic Logging:** monitors changes in acoustic properties of the formation caused by CO₂ injection;
- **Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR):** providing detailed information on pore structure and fluid content over time.

Despite the many options and applications available, logging has several drawbacks including restricted access to wells, difficulties with imaging, particularly when plume size is taken into account, cost, and limited depth of investigation. It can also be impacted by technical issues such as halite precipitation (IEAGHG, 2015). When we consider all these disadvantages logging becomes a less viable option for most situations.

1.8 Well Integrity Monitoring

Following the last section, geophysical logs are commonly collected after a well has been cased and cemented ("cased-hole") to evaluate the effectiveness of the cementing process and, particularly in later stages of a well's life, to assess the condition of the casing (IEAGHG, 2015). These methods are also applied to assess wellbore integrity at CO₂ storage sites where access to the wellbore is available. Baseline surveys and repeated assessments of post-injection are typically the minimum requirements for ensuring safe operations. A comprehensive evaluation of the integrity of wells that may come into contact with the CO₂ plume is often prioritised before storage begins to ensure containment.

However, some wells may be plugged and abandoned, leaving no current access. In such cases, integrity assessments rely on legacy data, including cement bond logs and abandonment schematics, which provide information on the depths and thicknesses of cement plugs (DNV, 2024). For wells where the integrity cannot be confidently determined, additional measures may be required. These could include remedial work or implementing mitigation strategies such as enhanced monitoring of the overburden to ensure containment and safety (DNV, 2024).

In the Netherlands, CCS wells are subject to strict well integrity monitoring requirements under the Dutch Mining Act and Mining Decree. Operators must develop a well integrity monitoring plan detailing methods, frequency, and criteria for assessing well integrity. This plan must be approved by the mining authority before drilling or operations commence. Monitoring should include both continuous and periodic assessments, covering the entire wellbore from surface to storage formation. Operators are also required to maintain detailed records of monitoring results, including anomalies and corrective actions, as well as perform regular inspections and pressure tests to ensure mechanical integrity.

1.8.1 Cement Integrity

Maintaining cement integrity is essential for well stability and CO₂ containment. **Cement Bond Logs (CBLs)** use acoustic and ultrasonic signals to assess the bond between cement, casing, and geological formations. These tools detect weak bonds, micro-annuli, or channelling, ensuring timely corrective actions (DNV, 2024). There are three distinguishable types of bonds:

- **Free Pipe:** No bond between casing and cement;
- **Good Bond:** Cement bonded to both casing and formation;
- **Partial bond:** Voids in cement due to micro-annuli or poor bonding.

Advanced tools like **Radial Cement Bond Logs** and **Ultrasonic Imagers (USIs)** provide azimuthal images, allowing precise localisation of bond defects and cement distribution (DNV, 2024).

1.8.2 Tubular Integrity

Ensuring casing integrity involves several inspection techniques, aiding in risk management. A few of the instruments that support casing integrity are highlighted in Table 1.

Table 1 - Tools for casing integrity, their application and limitations (DNV, 2024).

Tool	Application	Limitations
Cased-hole Callipers	Detects deformation, corrosion, or wear with precision.	Limited to detecting external wear.
Flux-leakage Tools	Identifies corrosion patches with 3D imaging.	Poor resolution for large-scale corrosion.
Electromagnetic Phase-shift Tools	Measures casing thickness for large-scale corrosion.	Lacks high resolution.
Ultrasonic Tools	Accurately measures casing thickness and diameter.	Does not detect mechanical damage.

Technical challenges such as halite precipitation and scale build-up can reduce tool accuracy, and advanced methods can be costly, but their inclusion in monitoring plans is important for regulatory compliance (DNV, 2024).

1.8.3 Annular Pressure Management

Annular pressure, the pressure between casing strings, is a critical factor in CCS well integrity. The mismanagement can compromise containment and safety (DNV, 2024). A handful of variables that may induce the build-up pressure are shown in Table 2, along with an example for each situation. To assure that everything stays in order there are some techniques that can be applied to help manage the pressure, such as:

- **Surface Monitoring:** Continuous pressure measurements detect abnormal trends.
- **Pressure Relief Systems:** Valves maintain pressure within safe limits.
- **Calculated Limits:** Maximum Allowable Annular Surface Pressure (MAASP) is calculated to ensure safety.

Table 2 - Causes that can induce pressure build-up.

Causes of Pressure Build-up	Examples
Thermal Effects	Expansion of fluids and evolution of dissolved gases.
Structural Issues	Hanger seal failure, loss of cement integrity, leaks in subsea valves.
Operational Factors	Ballooning of adjacent annuli, unforeseen pressure sources.

1.8.4 Regulatory Guidelines and Standards

To manage annular pressure effectively, there are some international standards and recommended practices which provide guidance on monitoring, limits, and mitigation, namely (DNV, 2024):

- **ISO 10427-1:2001**: Defines MAASP and MOP, ensuring operational safety during cementing.
- **API RP 90-1 (2021)**: Establishes Maximum Allowable Operating Pressure (MAOP) for annular spaces.

1.8.5 Monitoring and Testing

Regular monitoring and testing are essential components of annular pressure management to ensure well integrity and pre-empt potential issues (DNV, 2024). Table 3 highlights some of the key activities and their purpose:

Table 3 - Monitoring activities that help ensure well integrity.

Activity	Purpose
Pressure Monitoring and Trending	Tracks pressure changes, identifies abnormalities.
Well Barrier Testing	Ensures functionality of well barriers.
Operational Oversight	Identifies interdependent operational issues.
Equipment Checks	Verifies calibration and functionality of monitoring tools.

1.9 Fluid Sampling

Downhole fluid sampling is a valuable technique for calibrating and refining reservoir models, particularly those incorporating geochemical reactions (IEAGHG, 2015). It also plays a critical role in confirming CO₂ breakthroughs at wellbores. Laboratory analysis of reservoir fluids obtained through downhole sampling provides environmental data, including pCO₂, pH, HCO₃⁻, alkalinity, dissolved gases, hydrocarbons, cations, stable isotopes, and tracers. Wireline samplers and permanently installed tools like u-tubes are commonly used, with some systems allowing *in situ* analysis (IEAGHG, 2015). However, maintaining reservoir pressure during sampling is critical to avoid degassing, and tools like the u-tube lack offshore certification, limiting their suitability for unmanned platforms. Moreover, the accuracy of detecting CO₂ breakthroughs is closely tied to the frequency and timing of sampling.

Despite its importance, fluid sampling remains cost-efficient, with typical onshore costs of \$6,000–\$13,000 per sample, and cost reductions for bulk analyses (IEAGHG, 2015). Many projects have deployed fluid sampling in their monitoring plan such as Sleipner, Snhøvit, K12-B, Tomakomai, and others. This sampling methodology may also support the use of chemical tracers as described below.

1.10 Chemical Tracers and Sampling

Tracers can be defined as gases or liquid samples of exotic compounds which are injected and act as “fingerprints” (IEAGHG, 2015). These tracers are either soluble gases or exotic compounds that are injected into the CO₂ stream, either as a continuous flow or in pulses. Alternatively, the injected CO₂ itself may have natural signatures, such as its isotopic composition or noble gas content, which can also serve as tracers to provide information about the CO₂ origin and behaviour (IEAGHG, 2015).

1.10.1 Injection and Types of Tracers

Chemical tracers are injected alongside CO₂ into reservoirs to track its movement. This can be done either continuously or at specific intervals, depending on the monitoring requirements. The tracers can be (IEAGHG, 2015):

- **Soluble gases:** These include noble gases like He, Ne, Ar, Kr, and Xe, which are inert and have unique isotopic ratios that differentiate them from the natural background.
- **Exotic compounds:** Liquid or gas-phase chemicals designed specifically to act as markers in CO₂ streams.

These tracers can be tailored for specific applications, such as identifying the source of the CO₂, tracking its migration through the reservoir, or detecting potential leakage at the seabed.

Chemical tracers' primary application lies in tracking CO₂ migration within reservoirs, enabling the study of plume movement and flow pathways. By analysing tracer data, operators can estimate CO₂ volume and flow rates using downhole sampling techniques (Jenkins et al., 2015). Tracers also play a vital role in detecting and identifying leakage at the seabed. The unique “fingerprint” of a tracer not only confirms the source of the leaked CO₂, but also provides evidence of its origin, natural or anthropogenic (DNV, 2024). Additionally, tracer partitioning

between water and gas phases yields valuable information about reservoir interactions, such as dissolution processes and residual saturation trapping. Deploying multiple tracers with varying properties allows for the comparison of relative breakthrough times, which enhances understanding of fluid flow behaviour through the reservoir (IEAGHG, 2015). Nonetheless, it is important to distinguish two types of tracers, Isotopic and Chemical Tracers:

1.10.2 Isotopic Tracers

Isotopic tracers are naturally occurring variations of elements that differ in the number of neutrons within their atomic structure. For example, carbon isotopes are inherently present in captured CO₂ and can be used to track and monitor CO₂ in CCS operations. The isotopic “fingerprint” of injected CO₂ is influenced by its source, such as fossil fuels or atmospheric feedstocks, and by processes during capture and purification. This fingerprint enables the distinction between injected CO₂ and baseline reservoir conditions, provided the isotopic signature is sufficiently distinct from the surrounding environment (DNV, 2024). Flude et al. (2016), depicted some of the factors that affect the isotopic fingerprint of the captured CO₂, and what and how the tracers allow to track the nature of the CO₂, as portrayed in Figure 9.

Figure 9 - The isotopic signature of captured CO₂ is affected by various factors, such as the feedstock, processing techniques, and purification methods. Differentiating captured CO₂ from reservoir sources or shallow and surface baselines may depend on the use of a combination of intrinsic tracers (Flude et al., 2016).

The primary application of isotopic tracers is in monitoring CO₂ migration and breakthrough within storage reservoirs. These tracers help to identify CO₂ flow pathways, estimate movement, and provide insights into interactions within the reservoir, such as

dissolution into bicarbonates (Flude et al., 2016). Since isotopic tracers are inherent in the CO₂ stream, they do not require additional substances, making them cost-effective and environmentally benign. Moreover, their movement aligns with the CO₂, enabling early detection of breakthroughs at monitoring wells (Roberts et al., 2017).

However, the effectiveness of isotopic tracers depends on detailed baseline data for the reservoir, which may vary due to past activities such as hydrocarbon recovery or water flushing. Overlapping isotopic signatures in storage sites with multiple CO₂ sources can complicate monitoring. Nonetheless, isotopic fractionation during CO₂ dissolution often enhances their distinguishing ability, making these tracers valuable tools for reservoir monitoring (Flude et al., 2016). Costs for isotopic monitoring primarily involve sample collection and laboratory analysis, with per-sample costs estimated at \$2200–\$3300, excluding offshore collection expenses (DNV, 2024). Isotopic tracers have been effectively used in existing CCS projects to monitor CO₂ migration and reservoir behaviour.

1.10.3 Chemical Tracers

Chemical tracers are added to the CO₂ stream to enhance tracking, detection, and quantification of CO₂ migration and potential leakage. These tracers include natural components, such as noble gases, and artificial compounds, such as perfluorocarbons (PFCs) (Roberts et al., 2017). Noble gases are particularly effective due to their inert nature and non-reactivity with CO₂ or the surrounding environment, allowing them to migrate consistently with the CO₂. PFCs, on the other hand, are synthetic tracers with highly detectable signatures due to their low background concentrations in the atmosphere and seawater.

Chemical tracers provide precise insights into CO₂ behaviour, including flow pathways, reservoir connectivity, and leakage detection. By introducing tracers with distinct signatures, it is possible to identify the source of CO₂ and attribute it to specific storage operations. They also allow researchers and operators to quantify leakage rates under certain conditions, such as when tracers and CO₂ mix uniformly and migrate at the same speed (Flude et al., 2016).

Despite their advantages, chemical tracers face challenges. Artificial tracers, such as SF₆ and PFCs, can raise environmental and regulatory concerns, particularly in offshore environments (Roberts et al., 2017). PFCs, for instance, have a high Global Warming Potential (GWP), although their quantities in monitoring are negligible and pose minimal environmental

risks. Additionally, uneven mixing, phase partitioning, and adsorption onto sediments can affect the accuracy of tracer data (Roberts et al., 2017).

Costs for chemical tracers vary widely (DNV, 2024): PFCs are relatively inexpensive, with injection costs as low as \$1–\$110 per metric ton, while noble gases can add substantial costs, ranging from thousands to over \$1,100,000 per metric ton. Sampling costs further depend on the environment, collection method, and frequency, with laboratory analysis typically costing \$1,100–\$3,300 per sample.

Chemical tracers have been successfully deployed in onshore CCS projects, such as Frio and Otway, where they have been used to monitor reservoir connectivity and CO₂ migration (Jenkins et al., 2015; Hovorka et al., 2006). Offshore deployment, however, remains limited due to regulatory, logistical, and environmental challenges. By complementing isotopic tracers, chemical tracers provide robust tools for CO₂ monitoring, ensuring reliable detection and attribution in CCS operations.

In conclusion, both isotopic and chemical tracers are indispensable for understanding and managing CO₂ behaviour in CCS projects. It is important to note that these methods see their primary application in commercial projects rather than pilot, where there are multiple monitoring wells with a more complex monitoring plan/net. For a better understanding of chemical tracers, Meyers et al. (2013) supplied a very useful summary of these tools, on the other hand, Roberts et al. (2017) provided a schematic representation of the sampling environments for chemical tracers, portrayed in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - A schematic illustrating the sampling zones for offshore monitoring of leaked CO₂ and tracers, including their sampling environments and example methods. Catastrophic situation which monitoring intends to prevent (Roberts et al., 2017).

2. Seabed & Water-Column Imaging

Water column and sediment sampling are simple “generic” techniques for monitoring carbon capture and storage (CCS) projects. They are used to establish baseline environmental conditions, detect potential CO₂ leakage during injection, and confirm continued containment after the injection phase. These methods provide critical insights into the chemical, physical, and biological characteristics of the water column and seabed, ensuring the safety and integrity of storage operations (Uchimoto et al., 2019).

2.1 Water Column Profilers

Water column profilers, like CTDs (Conductivity, Temperature, Depth) probes, are instruments designed to collect detailed data across various depths in the water column. Profiler systems consist of vertically oriented probes equipped with sensors and samplers. Deployed from a vessel or platform, they provide continuous, high-resolution data during descent, either stored on the instrument or transmitted in real-time (IEAGHG, 2015).

This technology, widely used for decades, is highly effective in generating vertical profiles of water chemistry around specific locations, such as near wellbores or geological faults. However, its deployment requires careful planning, particularly in rough weather or challenging sea conditions, to prevent equipment damage or tangling. Despite these operational challenges, water column profilers remain an invaluable tool for CCS monitoring due to their ability to deliver real-time, site-specific data.

2.2 Water and Sediment Samplers

Water and sediment samplers complement water column profilers by enabling the collection of physical samples for laboratory analysis. These tools are deployed near wellbores or faults to establish baselines or to monitor conformance during later project phases. Once retrieved, the samples are analysed in the laboratory to determine chemical, physical, and biological properties that might not be detectable through real-time profiling.

Samplers vary in design and functionality, offering options to collect single or multiple samples, penetrate specific depths, or seal samples to preserve gases. This flexibility allows for a tailored approach depending on the project's needs. However, the process of collecting, transporting, and analysing samples can be time-consuming, and there is a risk of sample

disturbance or contamination during retrieval (IEAGHG, 2015). Despite these limitations, laboratory analysis provides a level of detail that surpasses on-site profiling, making this method a valuable part of CCS monitoring.

The choice between water column profilers and water and sediment samplers depends on project objectives, environmental conditions, and the type of data required. While water column profilers excel at providing immediate, high-resolution data, sediment samplers offer deeper analytical insights through laboratory processing. Each method comes with its own operational challenges and costs, which can vary based on equipment, deployment conditions, and analysis requirements.

2.3 Chemical Sensors

Chemical sensors monitor changes in seawater chemistry caused by CO₂ leakage, offering precise measurements of dissolved substances (IEAGHG, 2015). These measurements are conducted by using probes and are frequently employed alongside water sampling to facilitate shipboard analysis of various parameters including pH, partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂), dissolved oxygen, inorganic and organic carbon, nitrogen, phosphate, redox potential, salinity, and potentially isotopic carbon and chemical tracers (IEAGHG, 2015).

Several advanced chemical sensors are available on the market, designed to measure the aqueous concentrations of specific chemical components that are directly or indirectly linked to CO₂ leakage. Since seawater naturally contains a variety of chemical substances, including CO₂, at varying concentrations, these sensors must deliver reproducible and precise measurements. It is crucial that their readings reflect only the concentration of the targeted analyte, unaffected by fluctuations in other chemical components, or that these influences can be effectively corrected.

Unlike spatial sensing systems, such as sonars, chemical sensors operate as point sensors. This means that the target chemical must come into direct contact with the sensor for detection. In the event of a CO₂ leakage, the mixing of CO₂ into the water column is not instantaneous, resulting in a heterogeneous distribution of chemical species, complicating direct measurements.

To address this issue, models of physical and chemical processes in the water column, incorporating factors such as water currents and mixing dynamics, are used to estimate the

concentration of the analyte at locations distant from the sensor. These models help interpret sensor data and provide a broader understanding of the spatial distribution of CO₂ and its associated effects. Waarum et al. (2017) summarized some chemical sensors based on the parameter group, the measurable parameter, the depth rating and the producer. Some of the most common chemical sensors are (Waarum et al., 2017):

2.3.1 pCO₂ Sensors

These sensors measure the partial pressure of CO₂ in water, providing insights into dissolved CO₂ concentrations. These sensors rely on a gas-permeable membrane to separate the water column from an internal chamber where CO₂ is quantified. Biofouling and diffusion delays can impact sensor accuracy, particularly in long-term deployments. Despite these challenges, pCO₂ sensors are effective for detecting significant increases in CO₂ concentration.

2.3.2 pH Sensors

The pH sensors measure acidity changes in seawater resulting from CO₂ dissolution. While these sensors are sensitive, natural fluctuations in pH can complicate leakage detection. Regular calibration and understanding of baseline variability are critical for reliable measurements.

2.4 Sensors for Formation Fluids

Formation fluids are naturally occurring liquids and gases that are present within the pores of subsurface geological formations and are very important to be tracked during CCS projects as they are helpful for modelling reservoir dynamics. Some of the most common are water, often referred as connate water or formation water; hydrocarbons, gases, dissolved minerals and salts or fluids that have been injected (Bjørlykke, 2015).

Formation fluid sensors detect chemical components, such as salinity, trace elements, or hydrocarbons, that may accompany CO₂ leakage. These sensors provide early warnings by identifying significant changes in water chemistry near the leakage site. However, the limited availability of sensors for some substances poses challenges for comprehensive monitoring

(Waarum et al., 2017). Essentially, the primary purpose of these geochemical measurements is to ensure containment and provide comprehensive monitoring of the marine environment.

2.5 Seabed Imaging Tools

Seabed imaging encompasses a variety of technologies used to visualise and monitor the seafloor for potential CO₂ leakage. These methods can be employed to establish baseline conditions, monitor during the injection phase, and ensure continued containment post-injection (Uchimoto et al., 2019). Below is an overview of key seabed imaging tools, their applications, advantages, and limitations. Imaging technologies, such as side-scan sonar and video cameras, provide high-resolution images of the seafloor. These systems are very useful for detecting changes in seafloor topography or locating seep-related features in low-visibility conditions (Uchimoto et al., 2019).

The advantages of these technologies are significant, since they operate effectively in low-visibility environments and deliver detailed imagery of the seafloor. Sonars are especially useful for wide-area surveys, while cameras provide real-time, three-dimensional visualisation, enhancing the ability to monitor dynamic processes and detect anomalies. Despite their benefits, these tools have notable limitations. On one side sonars require specialised expertise to interpret images and differentiate signals from background noise, which increase data analysis. Additionally, deploying these systems is costly, as they often require mobile platforms like ROVs or AUVs. On the other hand, cameras, while offering real-time imaging, may lack the resolution necessary to detect smaller bubble streams in deep-sea environments limiting their usefulness.

2.5.1. Video Cameras

Video cameras provide high-definition imagery of the seafloor and are commonly used for monitoring bubble emissions, bacterial mats, and changes in marine life behaviour, which could signal elevated CO₂ concentrations at the seabed (IEAGHG, 2015). This mature technology is relatively easy to deploy and cost-effective, making it accessible for both short-term and long-term monitoring constraints (IEAGHG, 2015). These devices are widely used to observe bubble release and seepage patterns on the seafloor, making them invaluable for identifying potential CO₂ leakage. Additionally, these cameras can detect biological indicators such as bacterial mats or changes in marine life behaviour, which may result from elevated CO₂ concentrations at the seabed, as shown in Figure 11. One of the key advantages of video cameras is their simplicity and cost-effectiveness. They are easy to deploy and provide real-time updates on seafloor

conditions, allowing for quick assessments and monitoring. The high-definition images produced by these cameras further enhance the visual identification of features and potential leakage points.

Figure 11 - Video images of the seafloor taken with a camera installed on a ROV (IEAGHG, 2015).

However, there are limitations to their application. Image quality can degrade in low-visibility or turbid water, reducing their effectiveness in certain marine environments. Moreover, their operational depth is restricted by lighting and camera constraints, making them less suitable for monitoring in deep-sea conditions, and they are incapable of distinguishing the natural seepage of gases originating from the sedimentary column due to a CO₂ leak from the reservoir.

2.5.2. Seafloor Pressure Gauges

Seafloor pressure gauges are designed to monitor deformation of the seafloor, such as uplift, subsidence, or fault reactivation, caused by reservoir pressure changes. These instruments provide continuous, long-term data, making them indispensable for baseline and ongoing monitoring (DNV, 2024). These instruments are also versatile, often supplemented with additional sensors to provide comprehensive environmental monitoring of the near-seafloor environment. By detecting changes such as uplift, subsidence, or fault reactivation, pressure gauges can identify early warning signs of potential CO₂ migration or storage instability.

The advantages of seafloor pressure gauges are considerable. They are capable of continuous, long-term operation, making them well-suited for establishing baseline conditions and ongoing monitoring. Their integration with additional surveillance systems enhances their functionality, providing broader coverage for environmental and storage integrity assessments.

However, these systems are not without challenges. They are vulnerable to damage from fishing activities, trawlers, and maintenance operations involving seafloor infrastructure. In high-traffic areas, deployment and use of these systems may require the establishment of exclusion zones to prevent interference, adding to logistical complexity.

2.5.3. Acoustic Ranging Systems

Acoustic monitoring transponders (AMT) use precise acoustic pulses between seafloor stations to measure horizontal displacement and deformation. This method is used to track reservoir heave or subsidence with high accuracy and repeatability infrastructure (Dunn, 2019).

These systems measure horizontal and vertical displacement to detect plume migration and track the direction and speed of seafloor movement. By providing precise data on changes in the seafloor, they play a critical role in ensuring storage site integrity. The primary advantages of acoustic ranging systems lie in their high accuracy (5–10 cm) and repeatability (1 cm), which enable detailed monitoring of deformation (DNV, 2024). They can also be integrated with additional sensors, expanding their monitoring capabilities and providing a more comprehensive picture of storage site conditions. Furthermore, wireless data retrieval via unmanned surface vessels significantly reduces operational costs, enhancing their practicality for long-term use. However, their deployment and calibration demand meticulous planning, which can add complexity to their use. Additionally, the initial setup costs for establishing station networks and supporting infrastructure are high.

2.6 Active Acoustic Sensors

Active acoustic sensors are very useful for detecting gas-phase CO₂ leakage in CCS monitoring (Waarum et al., 2017). Their effectiveness lies in the strong acoustic impedance contrast between water and gas, making gas bubbles highly reflective to sound waves. These sensors operate across a range of frequencies and distances, providing flexibility for different applications. However, environmental factors such as seafloor topography, obstacles, and noise levels can limit their detection range.

2.6.1. Multibeam Echo Sounders and Sonars (MBES)

Multibeam echo sounders are state-of-the-art tools in marine gas seep detection. These hull-mounted systems emit wide transmit beams, enabling them to survey large areas with swaths up to several kilometres in deep waters. They provide high-resolution imagery and can

reveal characteristic gas flares in the water column. AUV-mounted versions operate at higher frequencies, delivering detailed seafloor images at the cost of reduced range. Multibeam systems are particularly valued for their extensive area coverage and flexibility in data processing, though their deployment requires significant energy and operational expertise (Waarum et al., 2017). Figure 12, by Blomberg et al. (2021), illustrates a data acquisition with resource to MBES mounted in a vessel. In the figure it is possible to distinguish the seep, characterised by the blueish model.

Figure 12 - Illustration of data acquisition with MBES on a vessel (Blomberg et al., 2021).

Also, Park et al. (2019), presented, in Figure 13, the results of using a MBES system for leakage detection, where it is possible to distinguish leakage through a controlled leak template at a rate of 5L/min.

Figure 13 - Multibeam sonar was employed to survey the area of interest, encompassing the leak frame and a controlled CO₂ release site. The top image depicts the area without a leak, with the red ellipse marking the location of the leak frame. The bottom image shows the sonar view during a controlled release of approximately 5 L/min of CO₂ (Park et al., 2019).

2.6.2. Scientific Echo Sounders and Fish-Finding Sonars

Scientific echo sounders are calibrated single- or split-beam systems capable of operating at multiple frequencies, making them ideal for detecting and characterising gas bubbles. Fish-finding sonars leverage their ability to detect air-filled targets, such as fish swim bladders, which are acoustically similar to large bubbles. These systems excel in estimating bubble flux and size distribution but are limited by their smaller area coverage compared to multibeam systems (Waarum et al., 2017).

2.6.3. Single-Beam Scanning Sonar

Single-beam scanning sonar creates detailed images by emitting a narrow acoustic beam. These systems are robust and cost-effective but lack the instantaneous imaging capability

of multibeam systems. Their high-frequency operation ensures excellent resolution, though their range is more limited. The slow scanning process can be a disadvantage when monitoring dynamic environments (Waarum et al., 2017).

2.6.4. Side-Scan Sonar (SSS)

Side-scan sonar provides high-resolution imagery of the seafloor, commonly detecting seep-related features like pockmarks or bacterial mats, capable of delineating objects down to 1cm or less, and produces a swath profile. Deployed via AUVs or towed vessels, these systems operate at high frequencies to maximise image quality. However, their imaging geometry makes detecting vertical gas flares challenging, and is only capable of producing 2D images, limiting their utility in detecting active seepage (Waarum et al., 2017; IEAGHG, 2015).

2.6.5. Synthetic Aperture Sonar (SAS)

SAS systems leverage AUV movement to create centimetre-scale seafloor images and bathymetry. Their ability to combine data from multiple acoustic transmissions enhances resolution and allows detection of fine-scale features. SAS systems can survey large areas efficiently but come with high operational costs and data processing requirements (Waarum et al., 2017).

2.6.6. Sentry Integrity Monitoring Sonar

Sentry Integrity Monitoring Sonar is an active sonar system designed to monitor seepage and leaks from the seafloor. It operates by emitting high-bandwidth, short-duration pulses and detecting echoes from objects in the water column, including gas seeps and CO₂ leaks. Deployed on a stationary lander, Sentry provides 360-degree coverage and can monitor over one billion cubic feet of seawater. Often paired with chemical sensors, it enables integrated monitoring of subsea environments. Sentry has demonstrated its effectiveness in detecting CO₂ leaks during an offshore CCS demonstration project in the UK.

Its ability to continuously monitor a large volume of water makes it ideal for both early detection and long-term observation of potential leakage events. However, its deployment and operation require careful planning and substantial energy resources, which can be a limiting factor for extended use (DNV, 2024).

2.6.7. Ocean Acoustic Waveguide Remote Sensing (OAWRS)

This is a technique used to model and quantify CO₂ emissions in the marine environment by integrating site-specific current data. At its core, the system uses an acoustic Doppler current profiler to measure ocean currents. By emitting high-frequency sound pulses, the profiler detects Doppler shifts caused by the movement of waterborne particles. Frequency shifts indicate whether particles—and thus the water currents—are moving toward or away from the instrument, providing data on current speed and direction. When combined with chemical sensors, OAWRS becomes a powerful tool for estimating the rate, depth, and direction of CO₂ leakage.

This data is critical for modelling CO₂ plume dispersion and assessing environmental impacts. Despite its precision, OAWRS requires integration with other measurement systems and advanced computational models to ensure accurate and comprehensive results (National Ocean Service, 2023).

2.6.8. Ocean Acoustic Tomography (OAT)

This technique utilises a network of transponders placed on the seafloor to measure the travel time of sound between them. The speed of sound in seawater is influenced by factors such as temperature, pressure, salinity, and seawater density. CO₂ bubbles leaking from the seafloor can alter these parameters, creating upward currents, dispersing the acoustic signal, or causing temperature fluctuations, which subsequently change the travel time of sound between the transponders. By continuously monitoring the travel time, this system detects variations that may indicate CO₂ leakage. Triangulation or tomography of the transponder network enables the mapping of these changes and can help identify the source of the leak. Acoustic tomography, first developed in the 1970s by Munk and Wunsch, has since been adapted for investigating bubbles and is considered a valuable component of monitoring strategies for CO₂ emissions detection.

When compared to other bubble detection techniques, which are often periodic and rely on ship or AUV deployments, acoustic tomography offers the advantage of continuous monitoring. However, it faces challenges such as biofouling, seafloor sedimentation, damage from trawlers, and the limitations of detecting weak or slow bubble streams. While passive acoustic systems using hydrophones are capable of continuous listening, they may not detect subtle acoustic signals from weak bubble emissions (IEAGHG, 2015).

2.7 Passive Acoustic Sensors

Gas bubbles in water emit distinct acoustic signals at various stages, including a characteristic sound when the bubble enters the water column from the seabed, oscillation sounds from gas-filled bubbles, and high-frequency bursts as bubbles burst or collapse. Passive acoustic sensors, such as hydrophones, are capable of capturing these sounds. However, the acoustic power emitted by bubbles is relatively low compared to the signals generated by active acoustic systems, resulting in limited sensitivity and operating range, particularly in environments with significant background noise (IEAGHG, 2015). These sensors have been successfully used to detect leakage from pipelines, where leaks are often localised at predictable weak points, such as flanges. In cases of leakage from pressurised pipelines, the high flux of escaping gas or fluid produces a concentrated acoustic signal, making detection relatively straightforward. However, for CO₂ storage site monitoring, the potential leakage locations may be less defined, requiring a larger area coverage and advanced detection capabilities (IEAGHG, 2015).

These technologies help distinguish leakage signals from background noise caused by marine activities, animal movements, breaking waves, currents, or rainfall. Methods to enhance detection include the use of directional sensors and deploying multiple sensors in array configurations. This approach improves signal-to-noise ratios and allows for more accurate localisation of leakage events. Passive acoustic sensors are valued for their low cost, robustness, and energy efficiency, making them particularly suited for long-term, large-area monitoring. Studies have demonstrated their potential for subsea leakage detection and quantification. Park et al. (2019) exhibits in Figure 15, the signal comparison of a 3L/min CO₂ bubble leak, a 1.15L/min bubble leak, and the background noise levels, where all the measurements were conducted with the same hydrophone systems.

Figure 14 - Passive acoustic monitoring of bubble release, with frequency plotted on the y-axis and time on the x-axis (Park et al., 2019)

To take full advantage of passive acoustic sensors, the proposed methods include leveraging passive acoustic emissions to estimate leakage rates and locations. Integrating passive sensors with renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind power, further enhances their feasibility for continuous monitoring. Additionally, these sensors can serve as early-warning systems, triggering active acoustic sensors for closer inspection and detailed verification of suspected leaks (DNV, 2024).

2.8 Environmental Monitoring

2.8.1. Sediment Sampling

Sediment sampling is a crucial technique in CCS monitoring, involving the collection of sediment material, often through simple grabs or cores that preserve pore water integrity. It is commonly combined with chemical and biological analyses to evaluate containment assurance, detect potential leakage, and assess broader environmental impacts. Sediment sampling has been implemented at prominent CCS sites such as Sleipner, Snøhvit, and Tomakomai, providing valuable data on geochemical processes and CO₂ interactions (IEAGHG, 2015).

This method serves several purposes in CCS monitoring, namely, to detect changes in seafloor chemistry and biology associated with CO₂ leakage. Analytical techniques measure parameters such as CO₂ concentration, stable isotopes, alkalinity, pH, and carbonate levels, providing insights into fluid migration pathways and storage reservoir interactions. Sediment sampling can also detect elevated concentrations of redox-sensitive species (e.g., iron and manganese), methane, and hydrocarbons, which may indicate leakage.

Additionally, sediment samples are instrumental in tracking the spatial footprint of CO₂ plumes and detecting trace metals or isotopes added as tracers to the injection fluid. Sampling near abandoned wells and storage sites offers critical information about lateral or vertical migration risks, especially post-injection. These efforts are often supplemented by contingency sampling when anomalies are detected.

The success of sediment sampling depends on the seafloor substrate and the techniques used. Substrates such as sandy sediments may facilitate core collection, while coarser or rocky sediments pose challenges. Tools like the Van Veen Grab are commonly employed, sampling approximately 0.1 m² per deployment. Vibrocorers are another option, capable of collecting intact cores up to 5 metres long, on sandy sediments. In finer grain sediments, sampling can even be conducted by piston-core.

Dedicated gas sampling methods, such as the Cone Penetration Test (CPT) rig with a sealed sampling head as well as Vibrocorers, offer enhanced preservation of *in situ* conditions but require rigorous pre-deployment testing. Other sampling methods, such as box-coring and piston-coring, are unsuitable for gas sampling due to their inability to maintain sealed conditions during retrieval. These methods are typically reserved for benthic fauna analysis rather than sediment gas sampling (DNV, 2024).

Special attention is needed when sampling in areas with high marine traffic, as instruments may be vulnerable to damage from fishing activities, wind farm construction, or infrastructure maintenance. Deploying exclusion zones around sampling locations may mitigate these risks. For ship-based operations, sediment sampling is often integrated with other surveys to minimise deployment costs. Costs for such combined efforts depend on operational scale, sampling density, and required laboratory analyses.

At Sleipner, sediment sampling campaigns have focused on total hydrocarbons, trace metals (e.g.: Pb, Ba, Cr, Zn), and microbial diversity. Between 2011 and 2013, sampling extended to include pH, dissolved organic carbon (DOC), and nutrients, providing comprehensive insights into seafloor chemistry and pore water conditions. In Tomakomai's case, sediment sampling efforts only included both pore water and gas analysis, addressing CO₂ plume interactions and assessing leakage risks. Similarly, sediment sampling at ROAD aimed to collect data on macrofaunal, geochemical, and pore gas conditions, contributing to robust containment assurance (IEAGHG, 2015).

2.8.2. Biomarker monitoring

Ecosystem response monitoring is a crucial element in detecting potential CO₂ leakage from carbon storage reservoirs. Elevated CO₂ concentrations, whether as free gas or dissolved in water, can cause a reduction in pH levels, leading to significant impacts on marine organisms. These changes affect biological systems as CO₂ interacts with cellular components, resulting in various physiological disturbances. Biomarkers—biological indicators sensitive to elevated CO₂ levels—have been identified as valuable tools to assess the effects on marine ecosystems and detect CO₂ emissions at the seabed (IEAGHG, 2015).

When CO₂ equilibrates between intra- and extracellular compartments, it leads to pH reductions in body fluids, causing physiological stress for many organisms. Such changes can result in behavioural alterations, shifts in metabolism, and impacts on community structures. Biomarkers, such as changes in behaviour or physiological responses of specific marine species, can provide measurable indicators of CO₂ leakage. For instance, benthic organisms like crabs or burrowing fauna might exhibit avoidance behaviours or altered community structures near leakage zones. However, distinguishing these changes from natural variability, such as scavenging or reproduction, poses a significant challenge.

Biomarker monitoring has been deployed at Sleipner and is planned for other CCS projects such as Goldeneye and Tomakomai. Tools like underwater video recordings and time-lapse sediment sampling have proven effective for observing behavioural changes and shifts in species distribution. These methods target organisms that interact with sediment-water interfaces, making them ideal for detecting early signs of CO₂ leakage. Sampling should prioritise methods that minimise natural variability to ensure accurate detection. Common techniques include Box-type corers and species-specific counts near suspected leakage zones (IEAGHG, 2015).

Despite its potential, biomarker monitoring presents cost and logistical challenges. Sampling and analysis costs typically range from around \$125 – \$380/sample, with additional expenses for manpower and processing. Furthermore, effective biomarkers for CO₂ monitoring have yet to be fully standardised, and natural behavioural variability complicates reliable detection (IEAGHG, 2015).

A noteworthy example of biomarker monitoring is the CO₂ReMoVe project, which focused on the deep-sea bivalve *Acesta excavata* in the North Atlantic. This species was tested

for its suitability as a biomarker due to its sensitivity to environmental changes. Specimens were exposed to elevated CO₂ concentrations for durations of up to 96 hours (IEAGHG, 2015). Researchers measured oxygen consumption, ammonia-N excretion, and acid-base parameters to evaluate the physiological stress responses. The study revealed that short-term exposure to elevated CO₂ caused acid-base imbalances and metabolic suppression, while prolonged exposure led to heightened stress responses. These findings demonstrated that *Acesta excavata* could serve as a reliable biomarker over extended monitoring periods. The species' responses provided measurable physiological changes, making it a valuable indicator of CO₂ leakage in offshore CCS projects (IEAGHG, 2015).

3. Recent Developments in Monitoring Techniques (Last 4 Years)

The following section explores various advancements in offshore CCS monitoring technologies and methodologies. It highlights the latest innovations and technological developments while also addressing the evolving mindset that is reshaping approaches to CCS monitoring. These changes reflect a growing emphasis on efficiency, environmental responsibility, and comprehensive monitoring strategies.

3.1 Integrated Monitoring

Integrated monitoring is an innovative approach of offshore Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) operations that helps to achieve the best monitoring “package” possible for each scenario. By combining advanced geophysical, geochemical, and environmental monitoring techniques, integrated approaches address the multifaceted challenges of offshore CCS, including plume migration, caprock integrity, and environmental impacts. This comprehensive monitoring strategy supports compliance with stringent regulatory requirements and builds public trust in CCS as a viable climate mitigation solution. One of the most significant advantages is enhanced leak detection. These integrated systems enable the early identification of anomalies, thereby minimising both environmental and operational risks. Additionally, integrated approaches improve cost efficiency by leveraging complementary technologies, reducing redundancies, and optimising the use of resources. This cost-effective strategy ensures that monitoring remains feasible even for large-scale CCS projects (Waarum et al., 2017).

Another key benefit is regulatory compliance. Integrated monitoring aligns with international standards, such as the EU Storage Directive and the OSPAR Convention and Guidelines, ensuring that CCS operations meet stringent legal and safety requirements. Furthermore, the transparency provided by integrated monitoring fosters public assurance. By demonstrating a commitment to environmental safety and robust risk management, operators can build trust in CCS technologies and address societal concerns regarding their deployment. This system is both composed of deep and shallow-focused monitoring techniques.

3.1.1. Deep-Focused Monitoring

Deep-focused monitoring techniques are aimed at understanding subsurface dynamics and ensuring the integrity of CO₂ storage within the reservoir, such as_

- **Time-Lapse Seismic Surveys:** seismic imaging is the gold standard for tracking CO₂ plume migration. By comparing seismic datasets collected at different times, operators can visualise changes in subsurface properties caused by CO₂ injection (IEAGHG, 2015).
- **Downhole Pressure and Temperature Monitoring:** Sensors installed in injection and observation wells continuously record pressure and temperature changes, which serve as early indicators of reservoir dynamics. Pressure anomalies may indicate migration through faults or caprock breaches, allowing operators to implement corrective measures before leakage occurs (IEAGHG, 2015).
- **Vertical Seismic Profiling (VSP):** VSP enhances near-wellbore imaging, offering high-resolution data critical for understanding injection behaviour and caprock stability. By integrating data from Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), VSP systems can provide continuous monitoring along fibre optic cables, reducing costs while improving resolution (Jenkins, 2020).

3.1.2. Shallow-Focused Monitoring

Shallow-focused techniques focus on detecting seepage, monitoring caprock integrity, and observing environmental impacts at or near the seabed. Some of these techniques are:

- **Acoustic Monitoring:** Acoustic sensors deployed on the seafloor and water column detect sound anomalies caused by gas seepage. These systems are particularly effective in identifying and localising bubble plumes, which may indicate leakage from the reservoir (Park et al., 2019, Blomberg et al., 2016).
- **Chemical Sensors:** Installed in the water column, these sensors measure changes in CO₂ concentrations and pH levels, providing real-time data on dissolved CO₂ plumes. Studies have shown that these sensors can detect dissolved CO₂ within a radius of 4–10 metres from the source, making them invaluable for environmental monitoring (Park et al., 2019).
- **Autonomous and Remotely Operated Vehicles (AUVs/ROVs):** These platforms are equipped with acoustic and chemical sensors to survey large areas of the seabed. They are highly effective for detecting structural changes or gas seeps in remote locations, as demonstrated in the Tomakomai CCS project (IEAGHG, 2015).

3.1.3. Integration of Datasets

The true power of integrated monitoring lies in the synthesis of datasets from various tools. Combining deep-focused geophysical data with shallow environmental observations creates a comprehensive understanding of storage site performance. For example:

- At Sleipner, seismic surveys identify potential leakage pathways, while pressure and temperature sensors confirm the structural integrity of the reservoir.
- At Tomakomai, 2D and 3D seismic imaging is complemented by water column monitoring to track both plume migration and environmental impacts (IEAGHG, 2015).

By using machine learning algorithms, operators can analyse these integrated datasets to identify patterns, predict anomalies, and refine monitoring strategies.

3.1.4. Real-World Applications of Integrated Monitoring

Sleipner CCS Project (North Sea)

Sleipner has been a global benchmark for CCS monitoring since its inception. Integrated monitoring at Sleipner combines time-lapse 3D seismic surveys with downhole sensors to ensure accurate tracking of a 17-million-tonne CO₂ plume. This approach has not only validated the safety of the storage site but also guided improvements in predictive modelling (IEAGHG, 2015).

Tomakomai CCS Demonstration (Japan)

This project employs a hybrid approach, integrating seismic monitoring via Ocean Bottom Cables (OBCs) with real-time chemical and acoustic monitoring. Its emphasis on environmental safety demonstrates how integrated monitoring can balance subsurface and ecological considerations (Park et al., 2019).

Northern Lights Project (North Sea)

Northern Lights adopts a multi-layered monitoring approach, combining DAS-based seismic surveys, environmental monitoring, and pressure sensors to establish a robust baseline and track plume behaviour over time (Jenkins, 2020).

To better understand the improvements, a deeper analysis of each technique update was done.

3.2 4D Seismic Surveys and passive seismic

Seismic surveys must contend with environmental issues, the cost of data acquisition, and the need for high-resolution data. Thus, the innovations must focus on reducing the environmental impact, and improving the quality and efficiency of seismic data acquisition. Some of the possible improvements point towards the development of low-impact seismic sources, more sensitive and broadband sensors, advanced data analytics, and integrating seismic data with other geophysical and geological data, and this leads to 4D seismics.

Seismic monitoring has evolved significantly, transitioning from the conventional 2D and 3D surveys to a more dynamic 4D approach. While 3D seismic offers detailed spatial imaging of subsurface geological formations, 4D seismic introduces a temporal component, enabling monitoring changes in the subsurface over time. This advancement is particularly important for offshore CCS projects, where understanding the movement and stability of stored CO₂ is vital. By comparing seismic data acquired at different times, 4D seismic provides insights into CO₂ plume dynamics, caprock integrity, and the effectiveness of storage strategies (Lumley, 2010). Regardless, nothing comes without a price, and in this case, a big one. Despite its power, 4D seismic surveys come with several challenges just as we saw before with 3D and 2D seismics:

- **High Costs:** The expense stems from the need for specialised equipment and highly skilled personnel to conduct 3D and 4D seismic surveys. This financial burden can be particularly restrictive for smaller projects or during the initial phases of site exploration and assessment;
- **Complex Data Analysis:** The collected data is highly complex and demands advanced analysis. Hence, accurately tracking the movement and distribution of CO₂ requires sophisticated computational tools and specialised expertise in geophysics and geology. This ends up presenting challenges in terms of the resources needed for analysis and the risk of potential misinterpretation of the collected data;
- **Temporal Resolution:** Although 4D seismic monitoring offers exceptional spatial resolution, its temporal resolution can be constrained. The intervals between successive seismic surveys are often dictated by budgetary and logistical limitations, potentially leading to less frequent data acquisition and the risk of missing rapid subsurface changes;
- **Environmental Concerns:** The use of tools such as seismic air guns and water guns, as well as other loud sources in some seismic surveys, particularly the ones involving water

guns, raise environmental concerns due to their noticeable impact on marine life, both the wildlife and the ecosystems (Mauro et al., 2024). These concerns lead to regulatory challenges and an increasing demand for environmental impact assessments, further adding to the complexity and cost of the projects.

Faced with these constraints, there has been an ongoing effort to develop sources that minimize conventional seismics' impacts while providing the required imaging capabilities (Ahmad, 2024). 3D and 4D apart, there have been some other innovative seismic solutions:

3.2.1. Multi-component Seismic: While traditional seismic methods only record the vertical component of the wavefield, M-CS uses geophones/hydrophones that allow to also record the horizontal wave movements, providing additional data which not only allow the differentiation between fluid types but also characterises fractures and anisotropy in the rocks better.

3.2.2. XHR Mini-Streamers: The monitoring of offshore carbon capture and storage (CCS) systems is crucial to ensuring the long-term integrity and safety of stored CO₂. Among the diverse technologies available, XHR mini streamers, where XHR stands for Extended High Resolution, have emerged as a transformative tool in geophysical monitoring. These compact, modular seismic tools offer significant advantages in resolution and cost-effectiveness, providing targeted data acquisition that complements broader monitoring frameworks.

Mini-streamers have been successfully deployed in various CCS projects, notably at the Sleipner field in the North Sea, as exhibited in Figure 15. Here, their capacity for high-resolution imaging was demonstrated in shallow water depths, where they enhanced the detection and delineation of CO₂ plume boundaries. Their ability to deliver sharper reflections and improved imaging of overburden layers has been particularly beneficial for tracking plume migration and ensuring containment.

Figure 15 - a) CO₂ polygon on Sleipner; b) A section from 3D-XHR image showing the CO₂ plume (Dehghan-Niri et al., 2022).

Unlike traditional large-scale 4D seismic systems, mini-streamers are less expensive to deploy and operate, allowing operators to focus their resources on specific areas of interest without sacrificing data quality. These attributes make mini-streamers great options for localized, time-sensitive monitoring needs, where traditional methods may be impractical or cost-prohibitive. By other words some of XHR applications/advantages are:

- **Localized Monitoring:** particularly effective for imaging shallow CO₂ plumes in offshore reservoirs, as demonstrated in the Sleipner field trials, where they provided detailed images of the overburden and enhanced plume reflection clarity (Dehghan-Niri et al., 2022).
- **Complementary Data Acquisition:** These devices are integrated with broader systems like PRM to address localized anomalies, ensuring comprehensive surveillance (DNV, 2024).
- **Cost Efficiency:** By deploying modular arrays tailored to specific sites, mini-streamers reduce survey costs while maintaining high-resolution capabilities (DNV, 2024).

Nonetheless, these devices face certain challenges that must be addressed to maximize their effectiveness. One significant limitation is their susceptibility to elevated noise levels. Due to their compact size, they have limited receiver and source sampling, thus, mini-streamers

often encounter higher ambient noise compared to conventional seismic methods, which mandates the implementation of advanced denoising algorithms to extract accurate and reliable data from the acquired signals (Dehghan-Niri et al., 2022). Additionally, mini-streamers are primarily suited for shallow target imaging, which limits their utility in deeper geological formations. As depth increases, their performance diminishes, making them less effective for monitoring CO₂ storage in deeper reservoirs (Dehghan-Niri et al., 2022). In Figure 16, Dehghan-Niri et al. (2022) illustrates how XHR excels versus conventional seismic in shallow situations, in this case, 0 – 150 metres deep.

Figure 16 - Adapted from Dehghan-Niri et al. (2022). (a) Conventional seismic repeat from 2020; (b) XHR image from 2020; (c) XHR image from 2021; (d) The difference between XHR-2021 and XHR-2020.

As mentioned before, Permanent Reservoir Monitoring (PRM) systems are designed to provide continuous seismic surveillance of CO₂ storage sites. By using permanently installed seabed sensors, PRM systems establish a detailed baseline of subsurface conditions and detect changes over time. While PRM offers unparalleled coverage and temporal consistency, it lacks the adaptability and high spatial resolution that mini-streamers provide. Thus, the integration of mini-streamers into PRM frameworks creates a complementary relationship, where mini-streamers address the limitations of fixed sensors by offering mobility and the ability to focus on specific anomalies (IEAGHG, 2015).

In practice, PRM provides the foundational data necessary for understanding broad subsurface dynamics, while mini-streamers add detail to specific areas where precision is required. For example, during the early injection phases of a CCS project, mini-streamers can deliver high-resolution snapshots of the developing CO₂ plume (Dehghan-Niri et al., 2022). This targeted approach enhances the overall effectiveness of PRM systems, ensuring that both macro and micro-level changes are captured. Such integration is particularly valuable in complex storage settings, such as those on the Dutch Continental Shelf, where overlapping surface activities and variable geological conditions demand adaptive monitoring solutions (Blomberg et al., 2021).

3.3 Full Waveform Inversion (FWI) and Reverse Time Migration (RTM)

3D and 4D seismic imaging are essentially the base for identifying subsurface CO₂ storage sites and monitoring any potential leakage. Reverse Time Migration (RTM) forms the foundation of this process, requiring numerical modelling to simulate forward and backward wavefields. The accuracy of these models is heavily dependent on a reliable velocity model, typically derived from Full Waveform Inversion (FWI). FWI and RTM serve distinct but complementary roles in subsurface imaging and velocity modelling. RTM complements FWI by focusing on imaging subsurface features through reflectivity modelling. This combination of techniques traces seismic wavefields back through a velocity model, delineating geological structures and boundaries (Shin et al., 2022b; Qin et al., 2015).

FWI is a computationally intensive process that iteratively refines subsurface velocity models by minimizing discrepancies between observed and synthetic seismic data. Its success relies heavily on the resolution and accuracy of input data, a need that mini-streamers are positioned to meet. These compact seismic tools capture high-resolution, localized seismic reflections, providing critical data points that enhance the precision of velocity models. Figure 17 illustrates the seismic imaging process between data and model spaces using FWI and RTM. However, there are some problems that we face with FWI, namely the local minima. Local minima occur when the optimization process becomes stuck in a suboptimal solution instead of reaching the true global minimum. This arises due to the objective function, which evaluates the difference between observed and modelled seismic data, having multiple minima caused by the complexity of the wavefield and subsurface structures. In this context, local minima pose significant challenges by hindering the accurate reconstruction of subsurface properties.

Figure 17 - A schematic representation of the seismic imaging process connecting data and model spaces using Full Waveform Inversion (FWI) and Reverse Time Migration (RTM).

Albeit the processes being composed by the same 4 steps, DAF comes as a possible answer to the RMT and FWI limitations:

- 1) **Acquisition:** 4D seismic data acquisition for baseline and monitoring data;
- 2) **Velocity Model:** Velocity model building using FWI;
- 3) **Reflectivity:** Reflectivity imaging using RTM with the background velocity model from 2);
- 4) **Differences:** Estimating CO₂ plume by subtracting two reflectivity images.

Figure 18 - Comparison diagram between the Conventional 4D Seismic Monitoring Process vs with the integration of DAF (Shin et al., 2022b).

3.4 Diffraction-Angle Filtering (DAF)

Diffacted seismic waves are produced by anomalies in layers such as layer boundaries, faults, and fractures. The outcomes of the FWI and RTM processes are highly influenced by the diffraction angle between the incident and diffracted rays on these anomalies. As illustrated in Figure 18, FWI and RTM which are based on the sensitivity kernel, will tend to utilise all wavenumber components from the seismic datasets. Since what we need to achieve high-resolution of CO₂ plume is a long-wavelength background velocity model for RTM and short-wavelength reflectivity, any unnecessary information will reduce the process's efficiency. It is important that some concepts are distinguished to better understand DAF, namely:

Low and High Wavenumber Components: the wavenumber refers to the spatial frequency of a wave, indicating how many wave cycles exist in a unit distance. Where:

- **Low Wavenumber Components** correspond to long wavelengths and represent large-scale, smooth variations in the model. They capture broad, low-resolution features such as large geological structures or long-wavelength background velocity models. In the case of seismic imaging, they are essential for constructing the overall framework of the subsurface, like identifying major stratigraphic layers.
- **High Wavenumber Components**, correspond to short wavelengths and represent small-scale, fine details in the model, which capture high-resolution features like faults, fractures, or detailed reflectivity of layers. These will assure detailed boundaries and sharp contrasts in subsurface properties granting better imaging.

Long and Short Wavelength Components: the wavelength is the physical distance between successive wave crests or troughs.

- **Long Wavelength Components** represent smooth and gradual variations over large distances, and provide information about the low-frequency trends in the data, often used to define the large-scale structure or background velocity models in seismic applications.
- **Short Wavelength Components** are rapid variations over small distances and provide details about the high-frequency content of the data, capturing fine-scale features and detailed boundaries.

It is important to note that these components characterisations are inversely related to each other and so when we talk about seismic and imaging, RTM and FWI we should understand that

long-wavelength (low-wavenumber) components are critical for defining the broad subsurface structure and mitigating issues like local minima in inversion and that short-wavelength (high-wavenumber) components are used to enhance resolution and accurately image fine details, such as layer boundaries or fault lines.

In this scenario, Diffraction-Angle Filtering (DAF) is proposed as an innovative technique that utilises a virtual source by artificially incorporating terms derived from the virtual sources of the elastic wave equation. It can be incorporated during FWI and RTM with different modes to segregate long- and short-wavelength components for each procedure, respectively. According to Oh et al. (2021) DAF can be classified into five modes by controlling the weight of each coefficient. Given DAF's ability to discriminate the desired range of diffraction angles, certain filtering modes like IV and V will optimise CO₂'s plume tracking (Shin et al., 2022b).

This method was tested in a synthetic environment based on the Volve oil field in the North Sea, demonstrating its significant potential to improve CCS monitoring and advantages when compared with conventional seismic monitoring methods, namely in terms of resolution, precision, and accuracy (Shin et al., 2022b). Some of the main advantages are:

- **Resolution and Precision:** Conventional seismic methods like FWI computing and RTM often fail to differentiate between long- and short-wavelength components effectively. This limitation leads to issues like local minima in FWI and blurred layer boundaries in RTM. DAF mitigates these challenges by applying mode-specific filters.
- **Enhanced Velocity Modelling (Mode IV):** Utilised in FWI to emphasise low-wavenumber components and reduce local minima, ensuring accurate velocity modelling
- **Sharper Reflectivity Imaging (Mode V):** Applied in RTM to highlight high-wavenumber components, sharpening boundary reflections between geological layers, making it easier to define them as well as the plume's boundaries which ease its tracking.

In Volve's oil field study the integration of DAF into various stages of the seismic process significantly improved the ability to monitor and map CO₂ plume dynamics within the subsurface. These surveys revealed notable changes in velocity, with a 6% decrease observed near the injection zone, which provided clear evidence of CO₂ presence and migration. The results from this study underscored the value of DAF in seismic workflows. Mode IV provided a well-defined velocity model that accurately identified the reservoir, ensuring a robust foundation for subsequent imaging. Meanwhile, Mode V improved the resolution of RTM-

generated reflectivity images, delivering sharper and more precise delineations of the CO₂ plume compared to conventional methods (Shin et al., 2022b).

Compared with other traditional seismic techniques, DAF also has the advantage of reducing noise sensitivity, improving computational efficiency, and enabling adaptive imaging tailored to specific geological conditions. Its precision in resolving complex subsurface geologies and enhancing velocity models makes it particularly interesting for offshore CCS monitoring. Furthermore, DAF's sharper imaging capabilities support early detection of potential CO₂ leaks, providing critical safeguards for marine ecosystems and ensuring the long-term success of these projects (Shin et al., 2022b).

3.5 DAS/VSP

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) has emerged as a very interesting innovation for the monitoring of offshore CCS operations. This technology, which uses fibre optic cables to detect and measure acoustic and vibrational signals along their length, is transforming how operators monitor CO₂ storage integrity, plume migration, and environmental safety. By repurposing telecommunications fibres as high-resolution seismic sensors, DAS provides an efficient, scalable, and cost-effective solution for ensuring the long-term security of CO₂ sequestration sites (Sinha et al., 2024).

The operational principles of DAS are grounded in the analysis of Rayleigh backscattering within optical fibres. When laser pulses travel through the fibre, minor perturbations caused by external vibrations or strain modify the backscattered signal. By interpreting these changes, DAS systems can provide spatially resolved acoustic and vibrational data along the entire length of the fibre. This capability eliminates the need for discrete sensors, enabling continuous monitoring across extensive areas. The technology has already demonstrated substantial value in CCS operations, including the detection of potential leaks and the tracking of CO₂ plume behaviour within geological reservoirs (Yu et al., 2023). Another important consideration in DAS applications is the type of fibre optic cable used. While various fibre types exist—such as single-mode fibres, multimode fibres, and specially engineered polarisation-maintaining fibres—single-mode fibres are predominantly chosen for DAS in CCS monitoring. Single-mode fibres are preferred due to their low attenuation, high spatial resolution, and ability to transmit laser pulses over long distances without significant signal loss. Multimode fibres, although capable of higher data throughput, suffer from modal dispersion, which reduces spatial resolution and makes them less suitable for precision monitoring.

Polarisation-maintaining fibres, though effective for specific applications requiring polarisation integrity, are significantly more expensive and complex to deploy, limiting their practicality in large-scale CCS projects (Donadello et al., 2024; Gorshkov et al., 2022).

DAS is revolutionising due to its extensive spatial coverage. Unlike traditional monitoring systems, which rely on discrete sensors placed at fixed intervals, DAS transforms a single fibre optic cable into a dense array of sensing points – dots – that can span hundreds of kilometres. Scattering dots are created using femtosecond laser technology, introducing controlled points of high scattering along the fibre. These dots improve Rayleigh backscattering, increasing the signal-to-noise ratio and allowing DAS systems to detect external vibrations and strains with greater accuracy (Gorshkov et al., 2022). This enhancement is particularly valuable in challenging offshore environments, where weak backscattering can limit traditional DAS effectiveness. In regions where submarine telecommunication cables exist, DAS can be integrated seamlessly, leveraging existing infrastructure to provide real-time monitoring without additional deployment costs. This capability has been underscored in studies of DAS applications in the North Sea, where it has proven effective in tracking seismic events associated with CO₂ injection (Donadello et al., 2024).

Additionally, one of its most critical applications in CCS is Vertical Seismic Profiling (VSP), where fibre optic cables installed in boreholes act as dense seismic sensor arrays. The introduction of scattering dots enhances the sensitivity of DAS in VSP, enabling the detection of subtle seismic signals that may indicate CO₂ plume migration or caprock stress. This capability surpasses traditional geophone-based systems by offering denser spatial sampling and reducing deployment complexity. Moreover, DAS's integration into existing telecommunication networks minimises costs, leveraging pre-installed infrastructure for large-scale subsurface monitoring (Gorshkov et al., 2022; Sinha et al., 2024). Dehghan-Niri et al. (2022) presented a good example that supports the affirmation of DAS as a good tool for conducting VSPs. Although it was not conducted in a CO₂ injector but rather a water injector at Johan Sverdrup field, it serves as a perfect testing site for this technology. In Figure 19, it is possible to note some raw shot gathers from the injector mentioned previously, in this case pre and post de-noising.

Figure 19 - (a) Time versus measured depth of a single shot gathered during a DAS-VSP acquisition in a deviated injection well, shown (b) After noise reduction (Dehghan-Niri et al., 2022).

Cost efficiency is another major benefit of DAS. By repurposing existing fibre optic networks, DAS reduces the need for deploying standalone seismic sensors, which are expensive to install and maintain in offshore environments. This reduction in hardware requirements significantly lowers the financial barriers associated with large-scale CCS monitoring. Furthermore, DAS systems are resilient to the harsh conditions of marine environments, including high pressures, corrosive elements, and electromagnetic interference, making them ideal for long-term deployments in offshore settings. Currently, the interrogators for DAS are still significantly expensive. However, they have a very long lifecycle and therefore, given the growing interest in DAS technology, a decrease in cost is expected to occur in the near future (Gorshkov et al., 2022).

The resolution and sensitivity of DAS are critical to its success in CCS monitoring. The technology can detect subtle strain changes and acoustic signals, enabling precise identification of subsurface changes associated with CO₂ plume migration. For example, DAS has been used to monitor the integrity of caprocks, the geological formations that act as barriers to CO₂ escape. In a recent study, machine learning models were integrated with DAS to analyse strain and

pressure data, demonstrating the ability to detect caprock breaches with high accuracy. This approach, tested on synthetic datasets simulating CO₂ injection scenarios, underscores DAS's potential for predictive and preventative monitoring (Ganesh et al., 2022).

DAS also excels in real-time monitoring, a feature that is invaluable for offshore CCS operations. Continuous data acquisition enables operators to detect anomalies as they occur, facilitating immediate interventions. This capability ensures that any deviations from expected storage behaviour, such as unexpected pressure changes or leakage, are addressed promptly, minimising environmental risks and operational losses. Studies have highlighted DAS's utility in integrating with other real-time monitoring tools, such as Permanent Reservoir Monitoring (PRM) systems, to create a comprehensive surveillance network (DNV, 2024; Jenkins, 2020).

Moreover, DAS offers unique advantages in environments where traditional monitoring tools are less effective. For example, in remote offshore locations with limited access to conventional seismic networks, DAS's ability to utilise pre-existing fibre infrastructure provides a cost-effective and scalable alternative. It also reduces the need for deploying active power sources at sensor sites, as the fibre itself acts as the sensing element, enhancing the technology's resilience and simplicity (Gorshkov et al., 2022).

Its integration with mini-streamers represents a significant advancement in CCS monitoring. While DAS excels in providing broad temporal and spatial coverage, mini-streamers contribute high-resolution, focused imaging, ensuring that both macro and micro-scale data needs are met.

DAS has shown potential in reducing costs and improving real-time monitoring capabilities by leveraging existing fibre optic networks (Ahmad, 2024). When combined with mini streamers, DAS can identify large-scale anomalies, prompting targeted streamer deployments for detailed investigation. For instance, in Japan's advanced CCS projects, DAS systems provided foundational surveillance, while mini-streamers added resolution to specific areas requiring detailed analysis (DNV, 2024).

The coupling of DAS and mini-streamers can also support AI-based processing workflows, where data from both sources is fused to enhance pattern recognition and predictive modelling. This approach not only reduces operational costs but also provides a robust framework for real-time anomaly detection and mitigation.

Despite its advantages, DAS faces challenges, including data processing demands and computing power. Advanced computational methods, including machine learning algorithms,

are increasingly employed to address these challenges, improving anomaly detection and signal interpretation. Furthermore, ongoing research into enhancing scattering mechanisms and optimising fibre design continues to expand DAS's capabilities, ensuring its adaptability to the unique demands of CCS monitoring in order to overcome its sensitivity limitations. Recent studies, such as Matsumoto et al. (2021), have explored the use of underwater optical cables as hydroacoustic arrays. While DAS-based technologies currently exhibit lower sensitivity than traditional hydrophones in the high-frequency range and comparable performance to piezoelectric sensors in the low-frequency range (below 10 Hz), their key advantage lies in the simplicity of enabling multiple measurement channels within a single system (Jenkins, 2020; Gorshkov et al., 2022).

3.6 Passive seismic source

Passive seismic monitoring leverages background noise generated by natural events, such as earthquakes, or by artificial sources like anthropogenic traffic (boats, ships, etc), as represented by Dozier (2021) in Figure 20.

Typically focusing on low-frequency signals (0–20 Hz), often referred to as low-frequency seismology, this type of monitoring captures energy from natural seismicity and seismic noise (Ahmad, 2024). It is a non-intrusive approach to study the Earth's interior, effectively utilising naturally occurring seismic energy to establish Earthquake Early Warning Systems (EEWS). Like mentioned before, this technique relies on the continuous observation and analysis of seismic waves from various natural and anthropogenic sources and can be combined with other techniques.

Figure 20 - Illustration of the ocean soundscape, showing natural and anthropogenic sources of underwater noise.

From Dozier, A., European Marine Board, JONAS Project. (2021). The Ocean Soundscape. URL:

<https://www.amydozier.com/todays-ocean-soundscape>.

Monitoring background seismicity before and during CO₂ injection is necessary for understanding potential temporal changes in stress states associated with CO₂ storage. While no significant seismic events have been directly linked to injection at CO₂ storage demonstration sites globally, smaller micro-seismic events have been detected and correlated with periods of high CO₂ injection rates and increased bottom-hole pressure (Ahmad, 2024). This phenomenon raises concerns that large-scale CO₂ injection could potentially trigger larger earthquakes. As a result, a passive seismic monitoring system is helpful for site characterisation and for detecting potential subsurface geohazards during CO₂ injection operations. Some of the key aspects of passive seismic sources and the monitoring process are (Ahmad, 2024):

- Seismic Noise and Ambient Vibrations;
- Microseismic Events;
- Earthquakes;
- Seismic Interferometry;
- Array Development;
- Temporal Monitoring.

One limitation of passive seismic monitoring is its dependence on adequate natural seismic energy to effectively penetrate and illuminate the subsurface structures of interest. In regions with low seismic activity or for specific targets, the signals may be too weak to yield the

necessary insights, often requiring active seismic methods to supplement the data. Despite this challenge, passive seismic monitoring is continually advancing, with ongoing research aimed at enhancing data processing algorithms and sensor technologies to optimise the extraction of valuable information from natural seismic vibrations.

3.7 Environmental Practices

Soft-start procedures, a key mitigation measure commonly used in marine seismic surveys, involve gradually increasing the energy levels of the seismic source to allow marine fauna time to move away from the area before full energy levels are reached, thereby minimising potential harm or disruption to their natural behaviours. Such practices are complemented by comprehensive environmental studies conducted prior to seismic operations. Companies are increasingly committed to performing detailed ecological impact assessments, which evaluate the effects of seismic waves on local ecosystems and propose strategies to mitigate ecological disturbances. The results of these assessments often lead to adjustments in survey timings, locations, and techniques to reduce environmental impact. Additionally, the industry is making significant efforts to develop alternative energy sources for seismic acquisition. A notable innovation is the advancement of marine arrays and vibrators, which provide a more stable and controlled energy release compared to traditional methods. These technologies offer the potential for a less disruptive approach to subsurface imaging, promising both reduced environmental impact and effective data acquisition (Malehmir et al., 2012; Waarum et al., 2017):

- **Arrays:** Array techniques have marked a significant leap forward in seismic source technology by utilising multiple sources fired either simultaneously or with precisely calculated delays. This method generates a broader, more uniform energy distribution compared to single-source approaches, thereby reducing inconsistencies and enhancing the quality and reliability of subsurface imaging as well as it ensures better penetration and resolution (Ahmad, 2024);
- **Marine Vibrators:** offering a promising alternative to traditional air guns, which release energy in sharp, explosive bursts, marine vibrators generate a continuous and controlled seismic signal. This steady energy release minimises acoustic shock to marine wildlife, addressing growing environmental and regulatory concerns. Moreover, the consistency of the signal from marine vibrators improves data quality, making it possible to achieve clearer and more reliable imaging.

3.8 Ocean-Bottom Multiphysics Nodes (OBMP)

OBMP nodes combine seismic and electromagnetic (EM) data acquisition within a single deployment. Unlike traditional single-purpose ocean-bottom seismic nodes, OBMP nodes are equipped with both magnetic and electric field sensors, allowing for simultaneous monitoring of resistivity changes and seismic properties in the subsurface. This integration reduces operational costs and enhances data density by enabling joint seismic-CSEM acquisitions during the same survey cycle (Menezes et al., 2023). Key features of OBMP nodes include:

- **Compact Design:** Miniaturised sensors improve operational efficiency and allow for denser deployment.
- **Enhanced Sensitivity:** Advances in magnetic field sensors demonstrate comparable sensitivity to electric field sensors for detecting resistivity changes, expanding the utility of CSEM techniques (Menezes et al., 2023).
- **Integrated Operations:** Simultaneous seismic and EM data acquisition reduces redundancy, streamlining logistics and lowering costs.

These nodes innovated offshore CCS monitoring by enhancing reservoir characterisation, caprock integrity assessment, and cost-effective long-term monitoring. These nodes provide high-resolution data on reservoir geometry and fluid properties, with time-lapse CSEM surveys effectively tracking resistivity changes caused by CO₂ injection, enabling the detection of fluid substitution and plume migration (Menezes et al., 2023). Additionally, the integration of seismic imaging with resistivity mapping allows OBMP nodes to identify caprock anomalies that could jeopardise containment. By enabling joint seismic and EM surveys, these systems streamline operations, reducing the need for separate campaigns and significantly lowering monitoring costs over the lifecycle of CCS projects.

Marlim R3D Project

The Marlim R3D project exemplifies the capabilities of OBMP nodes in offshore monitoring. Using a synthetic 1D reservoir model, researchers demonstrated that magnetic field data alone could achieve high-resolution resistivity inversions, comparable to electric field data. The project also highlighted the potential of OBMP nodes to detect time-lapse resistivity changes associated with water-oil substitution over decades of reservoir operation. These findings underline the effectiveness of OBMP nodes in monitoring CO₂ storage dynamics, offering a reliable, cost-efficient solution for long-term CCS projects (Menezes et al., 2023).

3.9 Muon Tomography:

Muon tomography is an innovative monitoring technique leveraging cosmic-ray muons to image subsurface density variations. Muons are high-energy particles generated when cosmic rays interact with Earth's atmosphere, to map density variations in subsurface structures. As muons penetrate rock, their paths are attenuated based on the density of the material. By placing detectors at strategic locations, this attenuation is measured and used to create high-resolution density maps (Kudryavtsev et al., 2012; DNV, 2024).

- **Density Mapping of Reservoirs:** Muon tomography provides detailed insights into subsurface density distributions, enabling operators to characterise reservoirs more effectively. This is particularly useful in CCS for identifying heterogeneities within storage formation.
- **Tracking CO₂ Plumes:** Unlike traditional seismic methods that rely on velocity contrasts, muon tomography directly measures changes in density. This makes it well-suited for monitoring CO₂ plume migration within storage reservoirs. Through the detection of density changes caused by the replacement of formation fluids with CO₂, it offers a reliable means of verifying storage conformance.
- **Caprock Integrity Monitoring:** The method's sensitivity to density variations also allows for the detection of potential breaches in caprock integrity, granting that it does not migrate to overlayers, assuring containment (Kudryavtsev et al., 2012).

Muon Tomography has a multitude of advantages, it is a non-invasive method as it does not require active sources, such as seismic waves. Thus, reducing environmental disturbance and operational disruptions, which is ideal for long-term monitoring (Kudryavtsev et al., 2012). It also assures high resolution in complex environments. Its ability to measure density contrasts with high precision is particularly valuable in offshore settings where there is seismic noise. Last but not least it complements seismic methods. While seismic tomography excels in providing structural images, muon tomography adds density-based insights, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of subsurface dynamics (Kudryavtsev et al., 2012).

Detectors offering optimal performance are typically based on drift chambers and scintillators. Drift chambers use gas that ionises when a muon passes through, enabling sub-millimetre spatial resolution and precise muon angle reconstruction. However, they often require an additional trigger to distinguish muons from background noise and typically rely on a constant gas flow, which is challenging to maintain in boreholes, thus, reducing its interest in

CCS projects. Scintillators, especially plastic ones, are widely used in large-scale particle physics and astrophysics experiments. These materials emit visible or ultraviolet light when excited by charged particles like muons, and this light is converted into electrical signals by photomultiplier tubes (Kudryavtsev et al., 2012).

Despite its advantages, muon tomography faces challenges such as deployment costs, detector placement logistics, and integration with other monitoring data remain hurdles to widespread adoption. However, ongoing advancements in detector sensitivity and data processing, supported by Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, are addressing these limitations.

3.10 Ambient Noise Seismic Tomography (ANST)

ANST relies on ambient seismic noise generated by natural or anthropogenic sources, such as ocean waves or human activities. By analysing the travel times of surface waves within this noise, ANST generates surface wave velocity models, which are used to infer subsurface properties. This passive approach is particularly advantageous for offshore CCS projects, and it can be applied for most of the necessary tasks:

- **Reservoir Characterisation:** ANST provides valuable insights into the velocity structure of storage reservoirs, enabling the identification of geological heterogeneities that may influence CO₂ migration. At the Aquistore storage site in Canada, ANST has been used to monitor velocity changes associated with CO₂ injection (Stork et al., 2018).
- **Leak Detection:** The method is capable of detecting seismic velocity anomalies that may indicate CO₂ leakage. However, its sensitivity to shallow leaks and small-scale changes remains a challenge, requiring integration with other monitoring technologies (Stork et al., 2018).
- **Caprock Integrity Monitoring:** ANST can highlight stress-induced velocity changes in the caprock, aiding in the early detection of potential breaches and ensuring containment integrity.

Ambient Noise Seismic Tomography (ANST) offers several advantages. It is a cost-effective method that utilises existing infrastructure and passive data acquisition, making it a more affordable alternative to active seismic surveys. Its passive nature enables continuous, long-term monitoring in real-time without the need for repeated surveys, reducing operational complexity and costs. Additionally, ANST is non-invasive, minimising environmental impact and

disruption, which is particularly beneficial for sensitive offshore environments (Stork et al., 2018).

However, ANST also has limitations. Current methodologies face challenges in detecting fine-scale changes in shallow subsurface layers, affecting its ability to accurately identify small leaks. Improving resolution often requires denser sensor networks and extended data recording periods, which can increase costs and operational complexity.

Future research aims to enhance ANST's resolution through advanced data processing techniques and denser geophone deployments. Integrating ANST with complementary methods, such as distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) and active seismic surveys, can provide a more comprehensive monitoring framework (Stork et al., 2018).

3.11 Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs)

Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) are a transformative technology in offshore Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) monitoring, offering advanced capabilities for seabed and water column surveillance. AUVs are robotic systems capable of independent navigation in underwater environments, guided by advanced path-planning algorithms. These vehicles are equipped with a variety of sensors, including acoustic, chemical, and visual systems, enabling real-time data acquisition over large areas. Innovations such as deep reinforcement learning and water level surface modelling have enhanced their ability to navigate dynamically changing environments (Li et al., 2021; Jack, 2021). The sensor payload of an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) can be tailored to specific monitoring requirements. For instance, it can perform detailed seabed mapping using side-scan or synthetic aperture sonar (SAS) to identify features such as pockmarks, bacterial mats, and bubble seeps, while concurrently measuring dissolved CO₂ levels, pH, oxygen, salinity, temperature, and turbidity (Blomberg et al., 2021). Figure 21, shows an AUV being deployed with a SAS system installed.

Figure 21 - AUV mounted with a sensor system for seabed mapping and water column surveying (Blomberg et al., 2021).

Overall, these systems have many applications that can be focused on three main areas/purposes:

- **Seafloor Mapping:** AUVs equipped with side-scan sonar and multibeam echosounders generate high-resolution bathymetric maps of the seabed, identifying structural changes that may indicate CO₂ leakage pathways (Li et al., 2021).
- **Water Column Monitoring:** Chemical sensors integrated into AUVs detect changes in dissolved CO₂ concentrations and pH levels, crucial for tracking leaks or seepage from CCS reservoirs (Li et al., 2021).
- **Pipeline and Infrastructure Inspection:** AUVs perform detailed inspections of CCS-related infrastructure, such as pipelines and injection wells, using visual and acoustic imaging to detect wear, corrosion, or leaks.

Advantages vs Challenges of UAVs

- **Autonomous Operation:** AUVs eliminate the need for tethering, reducing operational complexity and enabling deployments in remote or hazardous locations (Li et al., 2021).
- **Cost Efficiency:** By covering large areas efficiently without extensive surface support, AUVs lower monitoring costs compared to traditional methods.
- **Enhanced Adaptability:** Advanced path-planning models, such as those based on deep reinforcement learning, allow AUVs to adapt to dynamic underwater environments, improving their utility in complex CCS scenarios (Li et al., 2021).

Challenges and Future Directions

While AUVs have revolutionised offshore monitoring, challenges remain, including:

- **Battery Life and Endurance:** Limited energy capacity restricts the duration of AUV missions.
- **Data Processing:** Real-time analysis of large datasets generated by AUVs requires robust computational infrastructure.
- **Navigation in Unknown Terrains:** Enhancing AUVs' ability to operate in poorly mapped regions is critical for expanding their applications in CCS.

Future advancements aim to improve sensor integration, battery technologies, and autonomous decision-making capabilities, ensuring AUVs remain at the forefront of offshore CCS monitoring technologies.

4. Integration Of Advanced Digital Tools

Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Deep learning (DL), and the Internet of Things (IoT) are revolutionising offshore Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) monitoring by enabling more efficient, real-time, and integrated systems to ensure reservoir integrity and environmental compliance. AI and ML algorithms offer unparalleled capabilities in analysing large datasets generated by CCS monitoring systems (Ganesh et al., 2022; DNV, 2024; Ahmad, 2024). Figure 22, summarises how DL is a subset of ML, and ML is a subset of AI. Their applications include:

- **Anomaly Detection:** AI models identify potential leaks or irregularities in real-time by recognising patterns in seismic, acoustic, or chemical datasets that indicate deviations from baseline behaviour.
- **Optimisation of Monitoring Strategies:** ML optimises the placement and operation of monitoring equipment by analysing historical data to predict areas of high risk (Warrum et al., 2017).
- **Enhanced Data Interpretation:** Deep learning models, a subset of ML that relies on neural networks with many layers (hence its name), improve the interpretation of complex datasets, such as seismic or electromagnetic surveys, reducing false positives and increasing the accuracy of reservoir characterisation.

Figure 22 – Hierarchical representation of AI, ML, and DL (Ahmad, 2024).

At the Aquistore project, ML algorithms have been integrated with Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) systems to streamline data processing and enhance the identification of micro-seismic events linked to CO₂ migration, and has been proven to be a great tool to optimize MMV (Worth et al., 2014).

Internet of Things (IoT)

The IoT underpins the integration of various sensors and monitoring systems into a cohesive network, enabling:

- **Real-Time Monitoring:** IoT-connected devices provide continuous updates on parameters such as pressure, temperature, and CO₂ saturation, offering insights into the subsurface and immediate detection of leaks (Warrum et al., 2017).
- **Remote Operations:** IoT allows remote monitoring of offshore CCS sites, minimising the need for personnel presence and reducing operational costs.
- **Data Integration:** IoT systems unify data from seismic, acoustic, and geochemical sensors, enabling a holistic understanding of reservoir behaviour.

At sites like Sleipner and Tomakomai, IoT-enabled systems have proven crucial in integrating diverse monitoring technologies into streamlined frameworks, significantly improving efficiency and response times (Warrum et al., 2017). Combining AI, ML, and IoT in offshore CCS monitoring offers transformative potential (Ganesh et al., 2022; IEAGHG, 2015; Waarum et al., 2017; Jenkins, 2020):

- **Predictive Analytics:** Advanced ML models predict reservoir behaviour under various scenarios, assisting in proactive risk management.
- **Customised Monitoring Plans:** AI-driven analysis tailors monitoring strategies to specific geological and operational conditions.
- **Scalability:** IoT networks facilitate scalability, ensuring seamless monitoring across expansive offshore fields.

The integration of these technologies aligns with regulatory frameworks such as the EU Storage Directive and supports the long-term sustainability of CCS initiatives.

5. Conclusion

The evolution of carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies reflects the broader journey of innovation, from foundational seismic imaging techniques to the adoption of integrated, automated, and environmentally conscious monitoring systems. This progression has been driven not only by technological advancements but also by a fundamental shift in mindset. The CCS field has embraced a systems-thinking approach, balancing technical precision with ecological and societal considerations to address the multifaceted challenges of carbon mitigation.

Today's state-of-the-art CCS strategies exemplify this paradigm shift. Integrated monitoring approaches merge deep-focused methods for reservoir conformance with shallow-focused techniques for environmental integrity, ensuring comprehensive oversight. Integrated monitoring is rapidly becoming the foundation of modern CCS systems, uniting deep-focused methods—like DAS-enabled seismic tracking of CO₂ plumes—with shallow-focused techniques for environmental and integrity monitoring. By combining these methods into cohesive strategies, operators can detect, assess, and respond to anomalies across all stages of CCS operations. Advanced tools like autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) and digital analytics underscore a commitment to scalability, precision, and efficiency.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are transforming the CCS landscape by enabling advanced data integration, predictive modelling, and operational optimization. These technologies unlock new possibilities for analysing vast, complex datasets generated by DAS, mini-streamers, and other monitoring tools. They enhance real-time decision-making, improve risk management, and support cost-effective, scalable operations. These innovations have redefined what is possible, positioning CCS as a viable solution for achieving global climate targets.

Yet, the future of CCS hinges on addressing critical gaps and setting clear priorities. Key focus areas include:

1. **Harmonizing Standards:** The establishment of robust, universal standards will be crucial to foster consistency and reliability in CCS implementation across projects and regions.
2. **Reducing Costs and Enhancing Cost Efficiency:** Continued innovation must target cost reductions to make CCS technologies accessible to industries of all sizes, particularly in developing regions where decarbonization is most needed.

3. **Digital Advances:** Leveraging big data analytics, Artificial Intelligence, and Machine Learning to improve predictive capabilities, optimize monitoring plans, and enhance decision-making processes.
4. **Fortifying Integrated Monitoring:** Expanding the adoption of comprehensive systems that seamlessly combine geophysical, geochemical, and environmental monitoring to ensure containment and conformance.
5. **Engaging Communities:** Building trust with locals, stakeholders, and the general public through transparency, safety guarantees, and demonstrable environmental benefits is paramount to fostering broader societal acceptance. Involving local communities will allow to build trust and foster cooperation.
6. **Prioritizing Sustainability:** Future efforts must embed environmental stewardship within all stages of CCS, from monitoring and verification to post-injection care.

By aligning technological innovation with a forward-thinking, inclusive mentality, the CCS industry can transform into one of the most important global climate responses. Collaboration among scientists, policymakers, industries, and communities will be essential to unlocking its full potential. The challenge is immense, but so is the opportunity—to not only mitigate carbon emissions but also lay the groundwork for a sustainable and resilient future.

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Appendix 1

Catalogue of MMV techniques

TABLE 7
Tools, technologies, and techniques for monitoring geological CO₂ storage.

GEOPHYSICAL

SUB-CATEGORY	Monitoring tool, technology, or technique	Description of the application /data acquisition	Scope/special considerations for offshore Netherlands	What does the data inform about the site and what to do with the data	Domain	Monitoring purpose (containment/conformance)	Spatial coverage	Continuous or on-demand monitoring	Timing of deployment (pre-injection, injection, post-injection)	Advantages	Challenges	Cost range	Maturity/previous applications	References
SHALLOW	Finger (single-channel sub-bottom profiling [SBP]).	Single channel seismic data are recorded using very high frequency sources such as pingers/chirp, electro-mechanical devices (e.g., boomers) and electrical spark generators (sparkers). The sources can be hull mounted or surface, shallow or deep towed pinger, as shallow as 5-50 m (up to 300 m in exceptional conditions).	Shallow gas monitoring.	SBP informs about shallow faults and possible accumulation and/or conduits for escaping gas. In preparing the container complex it helps identifying monitoring locations (e.g., migration pathways).	Shallow geosphere.	Containment.	Typically done along 2D trajectories of several kilometers long.	The technology can be applied to areas of special interest (e.g., based on legacy data or reprocessed short offset 3D data).	Pre-injection (baseline) and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Low cost, easy to use and long established technology.	Low quality compared to boomers. Low depth of penetration. ~60 m maximum in ideal conditions. Penetration is less through gravel deposits, as well as very low permeability or gas-filled sediments. Penetration dependent on water depth (e.g., 2 m water depth = 2 m penetration, 20 m of water depth = 20 m penetration). Dutch offshore is ~30-40 m deep. In complex geology, 2D profiling has poor amplitude fidelity.	Typically part of a seafloor survey package (100k-1M EUR).	SBP is a well established technology in a range of water depths for the purpose of hazard identification offshore drilling, development, and pipeline routes.	IOGP (2015, 2017).
	Chirp (single-channel sub-bottom profiling [SBP]).	Single channel seismic data are recorded using very high frequency sources such as pingers/chirp, electro-mechanical devices (e.g., boomers) and electrical spark generators (sparkers). The sources can be hull mounted or surface, shallow or deep towed pinger, as shallow as 5-50 m (up to 300 m in exceptional conditions).	Localised monitoring of leakage at shallow levels.	SBP informs about shallow faults and possible accumulation and/or conduits for escaping gas. In preparing the container complex it helps identifying monitoring locations (e.g., migration pathways).	Shallow geosphere.	Containment.	Typically done along 2D trajectories of several kilometers long.	The technology can be applied to areas of special interest (e.g., based on legacy data or reprocessed short offset 3D data).	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Low cost and easy to use.	Low quality compared to boomers. Low depth of penetration. ~60 m maximum in ideal conditions. Penetration is less through gravel deposits, as well as very low permeability or gas-filled sediments. Penetration dependent on water depth (e.g., 2 m water depth = 2 m penetration, 20 m of water depth = 20 m penetration). Dutch offshore is ~30-40 m deep. In complex geology, 2D profiling has poor amplitude fidelity.	Typically part of a seafloor survey package (100k-1M EUR).	SBP is a well established technology in a range of water depths for the purpose of hazard identification offshore drilling, development, and pipeline routes.	IOGP (2015, 2017).
	Boomer/sparkers (single-channel sub-bottom profiling [SBP]).	Boomers operate in the frequency range of 500 Hz to approximately 4 kHz (resolution 0.1-1 m), and sparkers about 200-800 Hz (~0.75-1.5 m).	Localised monitoring of leakage at shallow levels.	SBP informs about shallow faults and possible accumulation and/or conduits for escaping gas. In preparing the container complex it helps identifying monitoring locations (e.g., migration pathways).	Shallow geosphere.	Containment.	Typically done along 2D trajectories of several kilometers long.	The technology can be applied to areas of special interest (e.g., based on legacy data or reprocessed short offset 3D data).	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Low cost and easy to use.	Low depth of penetration. ~60 m maximum in ideal conditions. Penetration is less through gravel deposits, as well as very low permeability or gas-filled sediments. Penetration dependent on water depth (e.g., 2 m water depth = 2 m penetration, 20 m of water depth = 20 m penetration). Dutch offshore is ~30-40 m deep. In complex geology, 2D profiling has poor amplitude fidelity.	Typically part of a seafloor survey package (100k-1M EUR).	SBP is a well established technology in a range of water depths for the purpose of hazard identification offshore drilling, development, and pipeline routes.	IOGP (2015, 2017).
	HRES 2D.	High-resolution seismic of the shallow geosphere max 1000 m due to limited source size, but recorded at much finer interval (2-4x).	Identify leakage outside the storage complex (depending on definition).	SBP informs about shallow faults and possible accumulation and/or conduits for escaping gas. In preparing the container complex it helps identifying monitoring locations (e.g., migration pathways).	Shallow geosphere.	Containment.	Typically done along 2D trajectories of several kilometers long.	The technology can be applied to areas of special interest (e.g., based on legacy data or reprocessed short offset 3D data).	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Low cost and ability to operate in areas with surface obstructions, but minimum distance from platforms typically >100 m.	For accurate delineation of gas pockets, CO ₂ plume 3D imaging is required. Seismic amplitudes used to identify gas accumulations are very inaccurate with 2D imaging and only useful for very bright anomalies as for example associated with shallow gas hazards. In very shallow water (~10 m) it is hard to record the shallowest layers due to the minimum required distance between source and receiver.	Typically part of a seafloor survey package (100k-1M EUR).	SBP is a well established technology in a range of water depths for the purpose of hazard identification offshore drilling, development, and pipeline routes.	Griffiths (2018).
	HR/HRES/UHR/ 3D (e.g., P-Cable, XHR and PIKSEL).	High-resolution seismic of the shallow geosphere has been quoted optimistically as 0-2 km, but this is highly dependent on locally conditions (water depth; gas clouds) and acquisition design due to shorter streamer arrays and higher frequency sources. HR/HRES/UHR has been recorded with 'bin size' as small as ~1.5 m. Compare this with a regular 3D survey 12.5 m (or 6.25 m for high-resolution reprocessed 3D). Source and receivers for HR/HRES/UHR seismic are towed at 2-4 m. Most HR/HRES/UHR examples show images less than 500 m deep.	Improves overburden interpretation and provides localised monitoring of leakage at shallow levels. Although in theory depths like Sleipner injection site could be achieved attenuation due to distributed shallow gas, hard seafloor and multiples may make it hard to achieve significantly the kind of bandwidth associated with HR/HRES/UHR seismic systems.	High-resolution and 3D recording allow for mapping overburden stratigraphy, faults, and complicated migrations paths and CO ₂ accumulations. It thus can be used to target monitoring areas for fluid escape and sampling to identify leakage outside the storage complex.	Shallow geosphere.	Containment.	HR/HRES/UHR surveys cover typically several 10s of square kilometers and most examples that achieve the high bandwidth are <500 m although depths up to 2 km have been specified by supplier.	The technology can be applied to areas of special interest (e.g., based on legacy data or reprocessed short offset 3D data).	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	For accurate delineation of faults, gas pockets, CO ₂ plume 3D imaging is required.	HR/HRES/HR seismic technology lacks the offset range required for effective de-multiplying. High-resolution 3D seismic technology where longer offsets are recorded is then more effective. Both technologies make use of small seismic sources and lack low-frequency energy and may, therefore, struggle penetrating through gas clouds. In very shallow water encountered in the parts of the southern North Sea, source-receiver distance (50-100 m) will limit imaging of the shallowest layers.	Small cubes (10-30 km ²) can be acquired in 3-5 days using existing research vessels. With mobilisation cost and seismic processing we expect a cost of 100k-300k EUR.	HRES/UHR/HR3D seismic technology has been offered commercially since 2008 and has been used for 3D seismic imaging of marine gas hydrates.	Dehghan-Niri et al. (2021). Osmond and Meckel (2020). Planke et al. (2009a, b). Waage et al. (2021).
	Enhanced surface rendering (ESR)/ bathymetry.	Rendering of bathymetry or high resolution shallow surfaces to with techniques like shaded relief. It provides a clearer picture of the topography by mimicking the sun's effects (illumination, shading and shadows) on pockmarks and other escape features.	Identify possible fluid/gas escape paths in the shallow subsurface.	Can be used to identify geologically recent migration path ways and potential hazards to seafloor infrastructure (e.g., submarine slides, shallow gas, and wrecks) and environmental impact (e.g., cold water corals; waste).	Seafloor.	Containment.	Typically recorded as part of hazard surveys (e.g., several square kilometers), but much larger areas can be covered. In deeper water 3D seismic surveys are used to covered 100s of square kilometers.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Low cost and easy to use.	Not good in shallow waters i.e., < 300 m (the Dutch sector of southern North Sea).	500 EUR/sq km, but much lower costs can be achieved if recorded as part of a larger survey program.	This is a well-established technology in a range of water depths for the purpose of hazard identification offshore drilling, development, and pipeline routes.	Dolan et al. (2012).
	State-of-the-art conventional seismic survey.	Streamer technology to record broadband (e.g., multisensor geostreamer), highly repeatable steerable streamer.	Identify plume movement with the injection store and surrounding storage complex.	Monitor movement of CO ₂ plume over time.	Deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Typical seismic surveys are done over 100s to 1000s of square kilometers to >5 km depth.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Well established technology to image deeper subsurface over large monitor area.	Significant amount of surface obstructions like wind turbines, and production platforms will make it difficult or impossible to record data efficiently or safely.	5k-10k EUR/km ² depending on water depth, size of survey and synergies with other objectives and nearby opportunities.	3D and 4D seismic is a well-established and proven technology.	--
DEEP	3D/4D high-resolution towed streamer reprocessing.	Short offset reprocessed streamer survey.	Identify plume movement with the injection store and surrounding storage complex.	The high-resolution and 3D processing allow for mapping complicated migrations paths and CO ₂ accumulations. It thus can be used to target monitoring areas for fluid escape and sampling to identify leakage outside the storage complex.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	High-resolution reprocessing of 3D seismic survey data have been done over complete seismic surveys (i.e., 100s to 1000s of square kilometers). In shallow water the minimum depth is determined by the source-receiver distance. Its usefulness declines as attenuation limits the bandwidth of the reflected seismic energy.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Low cost as based on reprocessing of existing seismic data. Provides good 3D imaging of shallow near surface.	Reprocessing for higher frequency requires in depth knowledge of limited factors of regular processing.	100-300 EUR/km ² . Large scale surveys (1000s km ²) have been processed efficiently for <100 EUR/km ² .	Reprocessing for higher frequency requires in depth knowledge of limited factors of regular processing. Has been very successful when done properly.	Lutz and Strijbos (2009).
	Ocean-bottom systems/surveys/seismometers (OBS) (using ocean-bottom nodes [OBN]/ocean-bottom cables [OBC]) (permanent/non-permanent) (nodal deployment/retrieval: ROV, nodes-on-a-rope [NOAR], free fall and auto recovery, AUV [in development]).	In ocean bottom acquisition, receivers can be either ocean bottom cables or ocean bottom nodes. OBS: Companies offer seabed solutions for a range of environments, from deep-water ROV node, shallow-water node and hybrid combinations with towed-streamer technologies. Some are light weight node system (6x more nodes in single ROV load; 30% more deployment efficiency; battery life for 150 days of continuous recording).	Seismic can be used to monitor CO ₂ movement over large areas and at least several kilometers depth.	Seismic amplitudes can be used to estimate pressure and CO ₂ saturation changes and thus build/calibrate subsurface models to demonstrate conformance and containment	Deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Full-field.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Better location repeatability and higher signal-to-noise ratio. Can be used in areas with lots of obstructions like wind farm or production installations. OBS can record shear wave (mode converted data) which can be used to look through gas clouds obscuring deeper geology. In deep enough water the interference with the seafloor reflection ('ghost') can be reduced to yield more low-frequency content.	Deployment and retrieval is more expensive than streamer technology.	A permanent setup (life of field seismic or LOFS) would require up to 10 repeat surveys to be more cost-efficient than a streamer survey. Non-permanent ocean bottom surveys are more cost-effective and can operate in areas where streamer surveys cannot go (offshore wind farms). Better suited for structure identification vs. fluid. Continuous efficiency improvements. Industry aiming to reduce cost to about 50% more than conventional survey. Cost highly dependent on setting (e.g., surface infrastructure or shallow water/deep water), but at least 2-3x as expensive. Cheaper than permanent system.	This is a mature technology and has been used for exploration and development of oil and gas fields. Proven track record (e.g., Sleipner OBN 3000 km ² survey).	Frømyr (2020). PXGEO (2021). SAExploration (2021). Shearwater GeoServices (2023). TGS (2023).

GEOPHYSICAL

	Low-frequency seismic source.	Seismic surveys can be executed with specially designed seismic sources that have lower frequency than a standard airgun array (from 7- ~2 Hz).	Seismic can be used to monitor CO ₂ movement over large areas and at least several kilometers depth.	Seismic amplitudes can be used to estimate pressure and CO ₂ saturation changes and thus build/calibrate subsurface models to demonstrate conformance and containment.	Deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Full-field.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and post-injection unless triggered by a non-conformance issue or regulatory requirement.	Low frequency seismic energy penetrates deeper into the earth, help seismic inversion and resolve thick layers (e.g., like a CO ₂ plume in a thick sandstone).	Similar to 3D/4D deployment.	Not available.	Recent application.	Elboth et al. (2022).
	2D DAS/VSP.	Distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) converts a fiber optic cable into an array of acoustic sensors and thus can be used for vertical seismic profiling (VSP). Can also be used to detect microseismicity associated with plume migration: see under Microseismicity.	Identify possible fluid/gas escape in immediate vicinity of well bore.	Changes in amplitude or travel time along the wellbore can be used to identify loss of containment.	Deep and shallow geosphere, focused along the wellbore path and between wells where DAS is deployed.	Migration of CO ₂ across the injection zone or to shallower formations, detect migration of pressure between wells, or detect induced fracture opening.	Along or very close to the wellbore.	Continuous.	Continuous.	Non-intrusive as it can be deployed on or inside the tubing, low cost, multi-well geometry, a single line/cable can be used for multiple applications (e.g., acoustic, temperature, pressure, and can get full well coverage fast).	Coupling of sensors to the borehole wall may be not sufficient in all cases to get good quality signal. In complex setting a three-component sensor may be required to identify energy.	Installation 500k EUR per well recording with rigsource and processing of data 10k-100k per survey.	VSP is a mature technology. DAS is relatively new technology. In Salah, Algeria: difficulty with number of sensors (see text).	OFS Fitel (2023b).
	Cross-well seismic tomography.	Recording seismic data between two or more wells. Velocity, reflection, and other sonic properties are measured to provide structural and physical characteristics in both the horizontal and vertical directions.	Detect migration of CO ₂ away from the injectors and between wells at a much higher resolution than seismic data.	Cross-well tomography has been successfully applied to detected a CO ₂ plume, but the ability to map the plume is dependent on well placement and proximity.	Wells and deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Due to the limited source strength requires the source and receiver well bore locations to be close.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and injection.	Crosswell tomography is often able to achieve resolution of several meters.	Due to the limited source strength requires the source and receiver wellbore locations to be close. It typically only provides information in a 2D section through the wellbores.	200k-1M EUR.	Cranfield, USA.	SLB (2011).
	3D/4D DAS/VSP.	Use of a vertical array of DAS or regular VSP tools to create 3D volume away from wellbore. This can be repeated over time to monitor CO ₂ saturation away from the wellbore.	Detect migration of CO ₂ away from the injectors and between wells, CO ₂ along faults and overlying secondary storage units in the complex. For the Rotliegend play, imaging below salt layers.	3D time lapse VSP is able to look in all directions away from the wellbore, but could be limited to detecting within a range of the VSP array in particular in the presence of high velocity layers as are present in the southern North Sea (e.g., anhydrite, dolomite).	Deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	3D/4D VSP is limited to the wellbore vicinity (approximately proportional to the recording depth). It is not possible to record at a long distance from the wellbore when high velocity contrasts prevent transmission of seismic energy.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and injection.	DAS recording is very efficient as the sensors stay in place it does not require extensive wireline operations that may interfere with other well operations.	DAS sensors measure wavemotion along the wellbore vs a regular VSP tool measures in three components. Due to raybending, the recorded velocities can significantly appear higher. It is not possible to record at a long distance from the wellbore when high velocity contrasts prevent transmission of seismic energy.	Installation cost DAS 100k EUR to >1M EUR per repeated acquisition of 3D VSP requiring mobilisation of seismic source vessel to record a 2D grid of seismic sources (100k-1M EUR per survey).	VSP is a mature technology. DAS is relatively new technology. In Salah, Algeria: difficulty with number of sensors (see text).	Hill (2015).
	SpotLight.	Identify through demigration a limited set of source and receiver locations that are most suitable to validate the movement of the CO ₂ plume.	Detect migration of CO ₂ away from the injectors and between wells.	Seismic amplitudes can be used to estimate pressure and CO ₂ saturation changes and thus build/calibrate subsurface models to demonstrate conformance and containment.	Deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Focussed on the expected development of the plume.	Nearly continuous.	Continuous.	Fast turn around a much lower cost than 4D.	Relies on accurate subsurface model to located optimal source and receiver locations. Can this work with potential stacked reservoirs or overburden velocity changes.	In offshore environment this still would require a low cost 'vessel of opportunity' as a seismic source (e.g., 10k EUR/d).	Proof-of-concept survey 2023 (the Greensand project).	Al Khatib et al. (2021).
	Microseismic.	Hydraulic fracture monitoring from induced or natural seismicity.	Monitor site integrity and CO ₂ leak detection.	Microseismicity has been used to detect faults within the storage complex and may detect breaching of seals.	Deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Determined by the magnitude of the microseismicity and background noise levels and the distribution of the monitoring wells/sites (typically <1000 m).	Continuous.	Continuous.	Noise issues can be high, high instrument noise floor.	Adequate distribution of sensors. At least 3 sites are required for accurate location of quakes.	0.1-10s M EUR if dedicated monitoring wells are required or 250k USD/km ² .	Well established technology and applied in fracking monitoring.	Goertz-Allmann et al. (2017). IEAGHG (2020).
	SeisMovie/ permanent source and receivers.	Buried source and receiver for optimum 4D repeatability.	Plume monitoring.	To be used similarly as 4D seismic. Changes in seismic amplitude can indicate saturation and pressure changes.	Shallow through deep geosphere?	Conformance.	Several examples of SeisMovie have been over limited area of one or more square kilometers.	On-demand, but at regular intervals.	Continuous.	Low cost data acquisition and fast turn around with minimal disruption to community.	Permanent sources have only applied onshore (DAS sensors could be considered permanent sensors).	Not applicable offshore.	The high repeatability has been demonstrated on the steamflood monitoring project Schoonebeek. Similar permanent source and receiver setup has been used onshore CO2CRC Otway project.	Zwartjes (2015).
	2D STAR seismic.	2D seismic profiles in 'STAR' pattern centered on injection site. Deployed at CO ₂ SINK pilot project.	Plume monitoring in areas with low coverage associated with 3D (e.g., due to limited accessibility of the well site).	To be used similarly as 4D seismic. Changes in seismic amplitude can indicate saturation and pressure changes.	Deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Star pattern of 2D profiles of several kilometers long. Records to similar depth as regular seismic.	On-demand.	Pre-injection baseline), injection and post-injection.	Faster and more cost effective than a full 3D survey due to novel array approach and high source and receiver frequencies.	Difficult to do safely offshore with surface obstruction.	Costs as 2D seismic ~0.5k EUR/km.	Not used much, but based on well established technology.	Giese et al. (2009). Ivancic et al. (2012).
POTENTIAL FIELDS	Controlled source electro magnetism (CSEM).	CSEM is a marine geophysical method mapping the subsurface resistivity. A horizontal electric transmitter is towed across a grid of seabed receivers while emitting an electromagnetic field. The recording data are used to invert the subsurface electric resistivity properties.	Plume monitoring, which could be applied to the shallow plays of the Cretaceous (Vlieland Fm) and Triassic only where salt is not present.	A CO ₂ or hydrocarbon bearing layer will exhibit a higher resistivity than saline formation water and thus this technique can be used to follow the CO ₂ plume.	Deep geosphere.	Conformance.	Can be done over large area, but with the typical survey source strength, a maximum penetration depth of 3 km is achieved.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Low cost compared to 3D/4D streamer seismic. CSEM is typically used where seismic is struggling to distinguish low from high saturation gas.	Low resolution, cannot be applied to stores below salt e.g., Rotliegend play. CSEM application to Sleipner/Utsira is a challenging task, probably mainly due to the shallow seawater as well as seabed pipes.	Estimated at 1k EUR/km ² .	Deployed at Sleipner and considered mature.	Park et al. (2013).
	EM (x-hole EM).	Cross-well EM imaging directly measures reservoir resistivity between two wells up to 1000 m apart.	Detect plume movement in the reservoir between well bores.	Cross-well EM has been successfully applied to detected a CO ₂ plume saturation.	Wells and deep geosphere.	Conformance.	The ability to map the plume is dependent on well placement and proximity.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and injection.	EM methods can better distinguish low saturation gas from higher saturation.	Resolution of EM methods is lower than, e.g., crosswell seismic. Requires wireline deployment that is costly in offshore setting.	200k USD/km.	Limited number of case studies known. Vertical electrical sounding: Ketzin CO ₂ storage, Triassic Stuttgart Formation, sandstone onshore Germany.	IEAGHG (2020). SLB (2009).
	Gravity.	Measurements of the gravitational field at a series of different locations over an area of interest. The objective of the survey is to associate variations with differences in the distribution of densities and hence saturation.	Detect plume movement across the storage complex.	Density changes due to gas depletion, water influx or CO ₂ injection impact the gravity field as measured at the seafloor.	Deep geosphere.	Containment, conformance or detecting CO ₂ plume movement in the reservoir.	Seafloor gravity surveys can be done across the area of review. A recent review of sensitivity of various methods discussed a survey for a 1400 m depth below mudline gas accumulation, where with a sensitivity of 2-4 μGal a vertical change in gas-water contact of 0.15-0.6 m could be detected.	On-demand.	Pre-injection and injection.	Forward modelling of CO ₂ injection in the Australian Otway depleted gas reservoir, approximately 30 m thick at a depth of 2000 m showed that surface gravity monitoring would not be able to detect the CO ₂ injection for the maximum allowed CO ₂ injection, but borehole gravity would be able to monitor at much lower levels of injection.	Inverse potential field problems, like gravity and magnetics, are inherently difficult to solve because they are ill-posed and do not have a unique solution. The effects of nearby production need to be accounted for accurately.	Gravity surveys can be combined with seismic surveys, but for an accurate time lapse surveys a stable concrete platform at the seafloor for benchmark sensors is required, which means that, although significantly cheaper than 4D seismic, cost for a seafloor survey can easily be more than a million dollars if ROV operations are required with further increase depending on number of repeat surveys. 1000s USD/km ² .	Successful application at Sleipner CO ₂ project.	Alnes et al. (2011). IEAGHG (2020). Sherlock et al. (2006).

WELLS

SUB-CATEGORY	Monitoring tool, technology, or technique	Description of the application /data acquisition	Scope/special considerations for offshore Netherlands	What does the data inform about the site and what to do with the data	Domain	Monitoring purpose (containment/conformance)	Spatial coverage	Continuous or on-demand monitoring	Timing of deployment (pre-injection, injection, post-injection)	Advantages	Challenges	Cost range	Maturity/previous applications	References
WELL INTEGRITY	Cement bond log (CBL).	An acoustic sonic tool operating at frequencies between 20 and 30 kHz. Cement bonding is inferred from the degree of acoustic coupling of the cement to the casing and to the formation. Properly run and interpreted, CBLs provide highly reliable estimates of well integrity and zone isolation. Recommend usage with a variable density log (VDL).	Quality of the annular cement bond around casings for well integrity verification prior to well operations.	Time-lapse (repeated) deployment of CBL after sufficient re-pressurisation and decompaction of the reservoir to assess effects of CO ₂ injection on cement integrity.	Legacy and operational wells.	Containment.	Length of wellbore.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline survey wells), injection (when workovers are conducted) and post-injection (prior to well abandonment [barrier verification]).	Well established technology, readily available and low cost to deploy.	Not a 3D borehole image tool and unable to detect small or subtle defects in the cement channels.	~10k EUR, depending on contractor package and bundle agreements with service provider.	Mature and deployed widely around the world. It has been a standard tool in oil and gas operations since 1950s.	Shell (2017).
	Radial cement bond log.	Radial CBL tools were developed to overcome some limitations of conventional CBL tools and to permit more accurate evaluation of cement distribution by providing the precise location of partial bond and channeling. These tools use one or more azimuthally sensitive transducers to evaluate cement quality around the circumference of the casing. Data from these tools are presented as individual log curves or as azimuthal images or 'maps' of cement quality generated by interpolating between the individual azimuthal measurements. In addition, each tool design also provides a conventional 5-ft (~1.5 m) VDL waveform measurement to provide information about the cement to formation bond.	Quality of the annular cement bond around casings for well integrity verification prior to well operations.	Repeated (time-lapse) deployment of the tool after sufficient re-pressurisation and decompaction of the reservoir to assess effects of CO ₂ injection on cement integrity.	Legacy and operational wells.	Containment.	Length of wellbore.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline survey wells), injection (when workovers are conducted) and post-injection (prior to well abandonment [barrier verification]).	Well established technology, readily available and low cost to deploy.	Limited resolution and may not be able to detect small or subtle defects in the cement bond. This may require additional logging runs or further testing to confirm results. Coverage area is limited to the immediate vicinity of the tool and logs may not provide a complete picture of the cement bond quality throughout the entire wellbore. Tool limitations, such as poor data quality due to poor tool positioning can impact the accuracy and reliability of the results.	~10k EUR, depending on contractor package and bundle agreements with service provider.	Mature, but largely overtaken by the use of ultrasonic tools.	SPE (2015a).
	Ultrasonic Imager Tool (USIT) for cement bond evaluation.	The USIT uses a single transducer mounted on a rotating sub at the bottom of the tool. The transmitter emits ultrasonic pulses between 200 and 700 kHz and measures the received ultrasonic waveforms reflected from the internal and external casing interfaces. The rate of decay of the waveforms received indicates the quality of the cement bond at the cement/casing interface, and the resonant frequency of the casing provides the casing wall thickness required for pipe inspection. Because the transducer is mounted on the rotating sub, the entire circumference of the casing is scanned.	Quality of the annular cement bond around casings for well integrity verification prior to well operations. The 360° data coverage enables the evaluation of the quality of the cement bond as well as the determination of the internal and external casing condition. The very high, angular and vertical resolutions can detect channels as narrow as 1.2 in (~3.05 cm). Cement bond, thickness, internal and external radii, and self-explanatory maps are generated in real time at the wellsite.	Repeated (time-lapse) deployment of the tool after sufficient re-pressurisation and decompaction of the reservoir to assess effects of CO ₂ injection on cement integrity.	Legacy and operational wells.	Containment.	Length of wellbore.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline survey wells), injection (when workovers are conducted) and post-injection (prior to well abandonment [barrier verification]).	Well established technology, readily available and low cost to deploy.	Requires specialized expertise and experience for use and interpretation of the data.	Can be >100k EUR per run. Should only be used if cost-benefit analysis demonstrates value.	Mature and deployed widely around the world. It has been a standard tool in oil and gas operations since 1990s.	SPE (2015a).
	Cased-hole multi-finger caliper tool.	Multifinger cased-hole calipers are used to identify changes in casing diameter as indicators of wear and corrosion. They are also used to monitor casing deformation. They can have up to 80 spring-loaded feelers or fingers, depending on the nominal casing diameter.	Identification of wear, corrosion or deformation of wellbore tubulars. Can be used in completion tubulars as well as in all permanently installed casing strings.	Repeated (time-lapse) deployment of caliper runs to evaluate potential deformation of tubulars which is used to derive differences in horizontal and/or vertical stress changes during CO ₂ storage (geomechanical model calibration).	Legacy and operational wells.	Containment.	Length of tubular.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline survey wells), injection (when workovers are conducted) and post-injection (prior to well abandonment [barrier verification]).	Well established technology, readily available and low cost to deploy. This is useful only for corrosion/erosion measurements in tubing or if a production casing has seen many more revolutions than planned due to sidetracks. Cheap using wireline.	The performance of the tool can be affected by tool limitations, such as mechanical failures, poor data quality or poor tool positioning. These limitations can impact the accuracy and reliability of the results. Interpreting the results can be challenging, as the logs provide measurements of the casing condition and interpretation may require specialized expertise and knowledge of the logging tool and well conditions.	~10k EUR, depending on contractor package and bundle agreements with service provider.	Mature and deployed widely around the world. It has been a standard tool in oil and gas operations since 1950s.	SPE (2015b).
	Magnetic flux leakage tool (MFL).	Tubular inspection tool using magnetic flux technology is used to determine changes in the pipe wall thickness. The tool can measure metal loss both internally and externally. Similar to the electromagnetic phase shift tool.	Flux-leakage tools can identify localized casing defects such as corrosion patches, pits, and holes as small as 0.2 in (~5 mm) on both the inside and the outside of the pipe.	Identifies potential tubular corrosion and when at set periods allows tracking of any corrosion in certain areas.	Legacy and operational wells.	Containment.	Length of tubular.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline survey wells), injection (when workovers are conducted) and post-injection (prior to well abandonment [barrier verification]).	Can identify localized casing defects such as corrosion patches, pits and holes as small as 0.2 in (~5 mm) on both the inside and outside of the pipe.	Does not detect large areas of corrosion. It does not see non-magnetic scale, which can degrade the sensor response. The tool is also affected by changes in the electromagnetic properties of the casing.	~10k-25k EUR, depending on contractor package and bundle agreements with service provider.	Mature, deployed widely around the world, limited use in wells as it is a little more of a complex tool to deploy.	SPE (2015b).
	Ultrasonic Imager Tool (USIT) for casing inspection.	Casing and pipe integrity via corrosion/wall thickness detection. USIT is an ultrasonic casing examination tool delivering ultra high-fidelity content and graphics through the most efficient collection, analysis, and communication. The tool is able to detect and quantifies casing deformation and corrosion affects over time. (multiple runs). The tool provides comprehensive data and imagery of casing-wall thickness, with overlapping coverage of geometry and metal loss features. Unlike caliper tools which take general readings to calculate averages, the ultrasonic tool takes hundreds of thousands of readings per meter to maximize accuracy.	Identification of wear, corrosion or deformation of wellbore tubulars. Can be used in completion tubulars as well as in all permanently installed casing strings.	Time-lapse (repeated) deployment of ultrasonic casing inspection tools allows to evaluate potential deformation and corrosion of tubulars. Periodically repeated runs can be used to derive differences in corrosion and in horizontal and/or vertical stress changes during CO ₂ storage (geomechanical model calibration).	Legacy and operational wells.	Containment.	Length of tubular.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline survey wells), injection (when workovers are conducted) and post-injection (prior to well abandonment [barrier verification]).	Can be run using wireline or slickline and can be used on a range of tubular sizes from 2-48 in (~0.05-1.22 m).	Requires a couplant for transmission of the ultrasonic signal.	~20k EUR, depending on contractor package and bundle agreements with service provider.	First developed in the 1970 the tool was a significant improvement over traditional electromagnetic inspection methods, which were limited in their ability to detect certain types of defects.	Deployment Matters (2023). QuestIntegrity (2023).
	Electromagnetic phase shift tool.	The electromagnetic phase shift tools take measurements that are averages around the circumference of the pipe. They lack the localized investigative capability of flux leakage tools and are best used to investigate larger-scale corrosion.	Investigation of larger-scale corrosion.	A valuable tool for inspecting the integrity of tubulars in wells. It has a non-invasive nature, high-accuracy, versatile, rapid inspection capability, and is cost-effective, make it a good tool for verifying tubular integrity.	Legacy and operational wells.	Containment.	Length of tubular.	On-demand.	Injection (if severe corrosion is detected or suspected in injection wells).	The tool is sensitive to large areas of corrosion and to gradual thinning of the casing. The sensors do not need to be in close proximity to the casing, so a single tool can examine a range of casing sizes. Similar to MFL, and is a cheap memory or e-line tool to measure corrosion in tubings/casings. In E&P, technique only used if corrosion is suspected/seen in the past. Currently, tools are sophisticated and can see up to three tubulars deep.	The tool has low spatial resolution and lacks response to non-magnetic scale. The alternating current magnet requires relatively high power, which makes the tools difficult to deploy in memory mode.	~10k EUR, depending on contractor package and bundle agreements with service provider.	First electromagnetic phase shift tool was developed in the late 1960s by Schlumberger. The tool, known as the 'Casing Inspection Logging' or CIL tool, was based on the principle of electromagnetic induction and was used to measure the thickness of well casing and detect defects such as corrosion, holes, and splits. The CIL tool was a major advancement in well logging technology and has been in use since then.	SPE (2015b).

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MONITORING															
Downhole wireless sensors.	Permanent downhole gauge installed in the upper completion which is used to enable wireless communication with down hole sensors. Allows both pressure and temperature monitoring in the annulus.	Monitoring of annular pressure in outer casing annuli with wireless transmission from sensors to the transponder located in the upper completion.	Allows monitoring of annular pressures below the wellhead without wellhead penetrations for electrical conduits.	Operational wells.	Containment.	Annular space.	On-demand.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (installation of system during well construction).	Ability to monitor temperatures and pressures with sensors designed to transmit data to the surface using radio frequency or acoustic signals, eliminating the need for traditional wired data transmission systems and using wire connections and penetrations through casing strings or packers.	Difficult to transmit electromagnetic pulse data through formations. System highly dependent on formation resistivity and not proven to work below salt/anhydrite layers (Zechstein Group). Replacement or service of sensors and transmitters may be a challenge. Wireless tools are also more expensive and less reliable than cable-deployed tools.	~100k EUR, including installation of sensors and data receivers at surface.	The first wireless downhole sensors were developed and used in around 2012. The technology was pioneered by companies such as Weatherford and Schlumberger, who developed and deployed wireless sensor networks for monitoring various downhole parameters such as temperature, pressure, and flow rate.	Emerson (2023). Expro (2023). Halliburton (2021). SLB (2020).		
Surface pressure measurements at the wellhead and x-mas tree.	Pressure measurements at surface, pressure at tubing head and annular pressures measured at the wellhead surface outlets for each of the respective annulus.	Monitoring of tubing pressure as well as annular pressures at surface can provide early warning signs of sustained annular pressures helping with well integrity monitoring.	Real-time monitoring of CO ₂ phase behaviour, CO ₂ distribution over injection wells. Used for hydrate prevention and leakage detection.	Operational wells.	Conformance.	Annular pressure.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (upon installation of wellhead).	Simple sensors installed on wellhead providing pressure data continuously.	Single sensor can provide error readings, ideally a backup sensor is also installed.	5k EUR with installation costs. Data acquisition and data interpretation are a separate charge.	Proven conventional technology.	Esposito (2018). Parker Hannifin Manufacturing (2016). Spartek Systems (2023c).		
Surface temperature measurements.	Temperature measurements at surface, pressure at tubing head and all annular pressures at surface measured at the wellhead outlets for the respective annulus.	Monitoring of tubing temperature as well as surface annular temperatures can provide early warning signs of annular integrity issues.	Real-time monitoring of CO ₂ phase behaviour, CO ₂ distribution over injection wells, and hydrate prevention.	Operational wells.	Conformance.	Annular temperature.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (upon installation of wellhead).	Measures temperatures at wellhead and x-mas tree.	Single sensors should be avoided and sensor placement is critical to ensure correct measurements are taken and sensors are not influenced by environmental temperatures.	5k EUR with installation costs. Data acquisition and data interpretation are a separate charge.	Proven conventional technology.	Spartek Systems (2023b, c).		
Downhole pressure measurements.	Downhole pressures can be provided by individual pressure sensors either by sensors connected with electrical cables or wireless sensor systems.	Monitoring of pressures in tubing and below packers using wired connections to surface.	Flow assurance and operations within pressure envelopes (fracturing). Evaluation of frictional losses. Hydrates prevention. Well leakage detection.	Operational wells.	Containment and conformance.	Tubing pressures.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (installation of well completion).	Measures downhole pressures and ideally installed below packer.	Requires wire penetration through the production packer, which is existing technology used in smart wells.	100k EUR, where installation of downhole sensors requires installation of cables clamped to tubulars and often also requires packer or wellhead penetrations, which need to be manufactured to specialized requirements.	Proven conventional technology.	Park et al. (2022). Tao et al. (2013).		
Downhole temperature measurements.	Downhole temperatures can be provided by individual pressure sensors either by sensors connected with electrical cables or wireless sensor systems.	Monitoring of temperatures in tubing and below packers using wired connections to surface.	Used for determining thermal fracturing and thermal envelope of downhole completion (tubing and downhole tool integrity).	Operational wells.	Containment and conformance.	Tubing temperatures.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (installation of well completion).	Measures downhole temperatures and ideally installed below packer at reservoir level.	Requires wire penetration through the production packer, which is existing technology used in smart wells.	100k EUR, where installation of downhole sensors requires installation of cables clamped to tubulars and often also requires packer or wellhead penetrations, which need to be manufactured to specialized requirements.	Proven conventional technology.	Park et al. (2022). Tao et al. (2013).		
Distributed temperature sensing (DTS).	Downhole temperatures can be provided by fibre-optic sensors with fibre installed inside tubing.	Distributed temperatures over entire well length in short spacings.	In an injection well, it would show where the CO ₂ is flowing, informing which is the coolest area in the near wellbore area and potential impacts fracturing rock around the injector well and phase changes of the CO ₂ in the near-wellbore area.	Operational wells.	Containment and conformance.	Tubing temperatures.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (installation of well completion).	Provides multiple data points along entire tubing length.	Limited spatial resolution, typically limited to a few meters, making it difficult to detect localised temperature variations in large-scale applications. High cost of DTS equipment for high-resolution systems. Systems are typically designed for temperature ranges between -50-300°C. The accuracy is dependent on a number of factors, including the quality of the fibre-optic cable, calibration of the equipment, and environmental conditions. Vulnerable to damage from environmental factors or physical disturbances. Large amounts of data are collected and need to be stored and analysed.	100k-300k EUR, where installation of downhole fibre-optic sensors also requires installation of the fibre with packer and wellhead penetrations.	New technology. Applied to QUEST CCS project Canada.	Halliburton (2020). Molenaar et al. (2012). SLB (2016). Weatherford (2023).		
Distributed pressure sensing (DPS).	Distributed pressure sensing.	Distributed pressures over entire well length in short spacings.	In an injection well, it would show where the CO ₂ is flowing, informing which is the coolest area in the near wellbore area and potential impacts fracturing rock around the injector well and phase changes of the CO ₂ in the near-wellbore area.	Operational wells.	Containment and conformance.	Tubing pressures.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (installation of well completion).	Provides multiple data points along entire tubing length.	Limited spatial resolution, typically limited to a few meters, making it difficult to detect localised temperature variations in large-scale applications. High cost of DTS equipment for high-resolution systems. Systems are typically designed for temperature ranges between -50-300°C. The accuracy is dependent on a number of factors, including the quality of the fibre-optic cable, calibration of the equipment, and environmental conditions. Vulnerable to damage from environmental factors or physical disturbances. Large amounts of data are collected and need to be stored and analysed.	100k EUR, where installation of downhole fibre optic sensors also requires installation of the fibre with packer and wellhead penetrations.	New technology.	Halliburton (2020). Molenaar et al. (2012). Optics11 (2023). SLB (2016). Weatherford (2023).		
Distributed acoustic sensing (DAS).	Distributed acoustic sensing.	Acoustic sensing using fiber optics to determine vibration.	Time-lapse repeated acoustic measurements provides input to estimating geomechanical properties and the change thereof during CO ₂ injection. Calibrating plume migration modelling.	Operational and monitoring wells.	Containment and conformance.	Tubing vibration seismic events.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (installation of well completion).	Provides multiple data points along entire tubing length.	Limited spatial resolution, typically limited to a few meters, making it difficult to detect localised temperature variations in large-scale applications. High cost of DTS equipment for high-resolution systems. Systems are typically designed for temperature ranges between -50-300°C. The accuracy is dependent on a number of factors, including the quality of the fibre-optic cable, calibration of the equipment, and environmental conditions. Vulnerable to damage from environmental factors or physical disturbances. Large amounts of data are collected and need to be stored and analysed.	100k-300k EUR installation of downhole fibre-optic sensors also requires installation of the fibre with packer and wellhead penetrations.	New technology.	--		

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Flow meters.	Measurement of injection flow rate of CO ₂ in a supercritical or gas state.	Tracking of flow and injected volume.	Interval and well allocation (downhole/surface). Accounting and fiscal metering.	Operational wells.	Conformance.	Volume and flow.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (installation of surface pipe work to the well).	Numerous flow meter types and manufacturers available.	Maintaining consistent measurement accuracy may be difficult between the various available types of meters. The ability to manage phase changes in the injection stream may also be challenging if they take place.	50k EUR, varying by flow meter types and material requirements.	Proven technology. Ultrasonic meters are used for the Sleipner project, whereas both the In Salah and Vattenfall projects employ orifice meters. Orifice plates supplemented by Coriolis meters are used for the Yates project. The Sheep Mountain project operates both turbine meters and densitometers.	McCrometer (2023).
Virtual flow meters.	Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) calculation of flow rate based on pressure, velocity and temperature.	Tracking of flow and injected volume.	Allows tracking of injected volumes confirming injectivity and storage volumes.	Operational wells.	Conformance.	Volume and flow.	Continuous.	Injection.	Does not require physical flow meter at the wellbore.	Calibration and verification of accuracy required.	100k EUR.	Proven technology for subsea wells.	Turbulent Flux (2020).
Gas chromatographs.	Analysis of fluid/gas composition.	Tracking of product composition and impurities.	Composition of various CO ₂ streams (producers).	Operational wells.	Conformance.	Flow.	On-demand.	--	Can be used prior to compression and can be done online.	Analysis of supercritical CO ₂ flow is more complex and likely requires laboratory analysis.	100k EUR, depending on requirements.	New technology for supercritical CO ₂ .	--
Radioactive bullets.	The basic principle behind this technique is that a small, radioactive bullet is placed in the reservoir and allowed to move freely as the reservoir undergoes compaction. The movement of the bullet is monitored using specialized detectors, allowing changes in the reservoir to be tracked over time.	Legislation with reference to radioactive sources downhole.	--	Operational wells.	Containment and conformance.	Reservoir near wellbore.	On-demand.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection.	Can be effective for monitoring reservoir compaction.	The use of radioactive materials can pose a risk to workers and the environment if proper safety procedures are not followed. Can also be expensive and time-consuming, and the accuracy of the measurements can be affected by a number of factors such as the bullet position in the reservoir, the composition of the reservoir rock and the presence of other materials or fluids in the reservoir. Other monitoring methods are available that may be safer, more cost-effective, and provide more accurate measurements. For example, fibre-optic monitoring tools, which can now be used to track changes in pressure and temperature within the reservoir, whereas 3D seismic imaging techniques can provide a detailed picture of the reservoir structure and changes over time.	--	Unknown when radioactive bullets were first used, but radioactive tracers are radioactive isotopes that are introduced into the soil and their tracking of movement using radiation detection equipment was first proposed in the 1950s, and the technology was initially used to study soil erosion and sedimentation in river systems.	Allen (1984). Ferronato et al. (2020).
Tilt meters.	Tilt meters are a type of monitoring device that can be used to measure changes in the inclination or angle of a wellbore. When placed in a well, a tilt meter can detect changes in the angle of the wellbore caused by subsurface movements, such as compaction or subsidence. Tilt meters can be an effective tool for compaction monitoring because they can provide continuous, real-time measurements of wellbore inclination, allowing operators to detect and respond to changes as they occur. Additionally, tilt meters can be relatively easy to install and operate, making them a cost-effective option for many applications.	Calibration of geomechanical models.	Plume migration and containment risk assessment through geomechanical model inversion, that is, inverting [the CO ₂ plume] pressure changes from measured deformations using a geomechanical model.	Operational wells.	Containment and conformance.	Reservoir near wellbore.	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection (well construction).	Highly sensitive and can detect even small changes in the tilt or inclination of stratigraphic formations. Can provide real-time monitoring of ground movement, allowing for prompt detection and response to changes in ground conditions, which can help prevent damage to infrastructure or property, as well as ensure the safety of people in the area. Non-invasive and can be installed without causing significant disruption to the surrounding area, making them an attractive option for monitoring sensitive or environmentally protected areas. Relatively inexpensive to install and maintain (onshore), particularly when compared to other ground monitoring technologies such as geodetic or GPS surveys. Can be used in conjunction with other monitoring technologies to provide a more comprehensive picture of ground movement.	Can be affected by external factors such as temperature, humidity, or changes in the local environment. These external factors can cause false readings or make it difficult to accurately interpret the data. Requires periodic calibration to ensure accurate readings and calibration, but can be time-consuming and expensive, particularly in remote or hard-to-access locations. Can also be vulnerable to damage from the environment or accidents. Repair and replacement can be costly and time-consuming.	~10k EUR, but does not include the installation of the short conductor pipe into the seabed nor does this include the costs of the cabling required to connect all the tilt meters and relay the information back to the platform.	The first tilt meters for soil movement detection were developed in the 1970s. In the following decades, tilt meters became widely used in geotechnical engineering and environmental monitoring for detecting soil movement and instability. Tilt meters are now used in a variety of applications, including landslide monitoring, ground subsidence, and deformation monitoring for engineering structures such as dams and bridges.	GEO-Instruments (2023). GEOKON (2023). Measurand (2023). Nova Ventures (2023). Senceive (2023). van der Gaag (2017).

PETROPHYSICAL

SUB-CATEGORY	Monitoring tool, technology, or technique	Description of the application /data acquisition	Scope/special considerations for offshore Netherlands	What does the data inform about the site and what to do with the data	Domain	Monitoring purpose (containment/conformance)	Spatial coverage	Continuous or on-demand monitoring	Timing of deployment (pre-injection, injection, post-injection)	Advantages	Challenges	Cost range	Maturity/previous applications	References
TIME-LAPSE MONITORING	Time-lapse pulsed neutron (PNL) (also called Sigma (SIGM model) or time lapse saturation logging.	A classic reservoir management tool for understanding fluid distribution in a reservoir. When applied to CO ₂ storage projects, a PNL can determine CO ₂ saturation along the near-wellbore area. PNL determines the thermal decay of neutrons, by bombarding the formation, the pulse of neutrons, resulting in gamma rays being produced by the rock and measuring the decay rate of gamma ray response. The recorded gamma rays are analysed to interpret fluid saturation. In the SIGM model, the tool can differentiate between hydrocarbons, CO ₂ and brine. Quantify the CO ₂ saturated zones in the near well bore area, also determine the vertical distribution of CO ₂ in the injection zone and check if CO ₂ has migrated out of the injection zone up into and above the primary seal. Depending on the use and location of monitoring wells in the injection, PNL logging can identify CO ₂ plume migration, i.e., from the injection well to monitoring wells. When PNL runs are combined with other geophysical data, e.g., VSP, they are used to verify store containment.	Special considerations for the spallation neutron source (SNS): the Rotliegend Group has a complex mineralogy and fine clay content, which can affect the saturation of gas across formations. In depleted fields, its not uncommon to find residual gas below the FWL, e.g., there is residual gas trapped on the fine clay minerals 46 m below the FWL in the Groningen field. Petrophysical models calibrated to core are required prior to drilling to understand the impact of the mineral composition on gas saturation. The tool could possibly identify salt plugging due to super critical CO ₂ drying out hyper saline brine formations. The Rotliegend formation has hyper saline brine, injection of supercritical CO ₂ can dry out the brine and cause halite precipitation. Typically the risk of halite plugging is identified in the site characterisation stage and can be mitigated with inhibitors.	Well integrity when combined with other well integrity monitoring tools such as DTS on the casing (see Quest example). Informs the operator about near-wellbore saturations and detects if CO ₂ is migrating above the primary seal. Best combined with geophysical observations (e.g., from VSPs or 3D seismic) to provide a wider special interpretation of CO ₂ saturations and location of the CO ₂ front. The data will be used to update and calibrate dynamic flow models. The use of the SIGM mode PNL and 3D VSPs has reduced the need for full 3D surveys over project areas (e.g., Quest).	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Vertical profile along the wellbore, focusing mainly on the deep geosphere of the injection zone.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Can be run in cased holes and easy to deploy. Modern tools have slim housings, which reduced the need to pull the tubing for a logging run. Some manufacturers claim the tool can be run while the well is flowing, with no need to kill the well prior to logging. Can be used for diagnosis of potential completion issues.	In low-salinity formations waters (<5000 ppm), the PNL is challenging. The Netherlands does not have low-salinity environments. Baselines are key, however, in a depleted field they are critical due to the mix of fluid types. Lithology can impact saturation interpretations if not incorporated in the baseline studies and post-processing analyses. Some of the latest tools from logging service companies are working to overcome these lithological challenges with tools such as the RSTPro from SLB.	100ks EUR.	Mature and deployed successfully at Quest and Otway (pilot) projects.	Rock et al. (2017). SLB (2023b). van Elk and Doornhof (2017).
	Time-lapse neutron.	Identify the location of CO ₂ at the well bore. The neutron tool measures H ¹ of the fluid in fluid filled pores. CO ₂ does not contain H ¹ , so CO ₂ can be identified in the near well bore region super-critical CO ₂ displaces formation water, the neutron porosity log senses the reduction in formation hydrogen index and registers a reduction in apparent porosity.	Monitoring CO ₂ plume movement.	Similar to PNL (above), but lower resolution.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Vertical profile along the wellbore, focusing mainly on the deep geosphere of the injection zone.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Lower cost compared to PNL tools and can be run in cased holes.	Challenge in low-porosity, low-salinity zones. SIGM logging is superior for saturation logging.	100ks EUR.	Mature.	Xue et al. (2006).
	Time-lapse resistivity/ induction logging (cased holed).	Detects changes in formation resistivity associated with the presence of CO ₂ . CO ₂ is non-conductive and non-wetting, its displacement of formation water will generate an increase in formation resistivity.	Formation evaluation and monitoring CO ₂ plume movement.	Changes in formation resistivity can help detect plume movement across the injection zone. Best results when combined with geophysical techniques where appropriate.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Vertical profile along the wellbore, focusing mainly on the deep geosphere of the injection zone.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Used to tract CO ₂ plume migration within the store and potentially above it.	Hydrocarbons are resistive, and it could be challenging to detect a signal so in a depleted field setting. The technique is also not as reliable with low CO ₂ saturations in low-salinity formations. Requires non-conductive casing (e.g., fibreglass) in the monitoring wellbore.	100ks EUR.	Well-establish technology proven to work at Nagaoka, Japan.	Nakajima and Xue (2013).
	Production logging tool (PLT).	Injectivity logging for identifying injection flow profiles.	Monitor the depths/perforations into which CO ₂ is injected, as well as the injection efficiency at different depths. This can tie to injectivity and plume movement evaluations.	Reservoir compartmentalisation/ connectivity might result in a change in injection strategy.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Vertical profile along the wellbore, focusing mainly on the deep geosphere of the injection zone.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Standard O&G tool.	Can require experience to interpret logging results.	100ks EUR.	Mature and used at the Snohvit project when unexpected injection issues where encountered.	Hansen et al. (2013).
	Time-lapse temperature logging.	Time lapse temperature measurements providing insights into where injected fluids are going within the reservoir.	CO ₂ cools as it expands, and temperature can be used to support the evaluation of CO ₂ injection and movement through a reservoir over time	Knowledge of subsurface temperatures is important for understanding CO ₂ phase behavior and the injection profile.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Vertical profile along the wellbore, focusing mainly on the deep geosphere of the injection zone.	On-demand (usually combined with a PLT).	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Can be run while CO ₂ is injected.	Resolution is not always sufficient to identify detailed injection profiles or CO ₂ movement. Recommend to use in conjunction with other evaluation technologies.	100ks EUR.	Mature and used in a wide variety of applications.	Park et al. (2022). Tao et al. (2013).
	Time-lapse sonic logging.	Measures acoustic properties of rock and fluids, such as the compressional and shear velocity (P- and S-wave velocity). Sonic log velocity should slow down in the presence of CO ₂ .	Can be used to support the evaluation of CO ₂ injection and movement through a reservoir over time. This can also be used in conjunction with 3D/4D seismic surveys.	Sonic logs could track the movement of CO ₂ across the injection zone between wellbores.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Vertical profile along the wellbore, focusing mainly on the deep geosphere of the injection zone.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Can be done cased holes.	Low resolution compared to PNL due to the compressibility of supercritical CO ₂ . The contrast in compressional velocity is too low to be sensitive enough to detect saturation changes after initial CO ₂ injection. In a depleted field setting, the signal might not be sufficient to distinguish between hydrocarbons and CO ₂ , as both will reduce the sonic velocity.	100ks EUR.	Mature O&G industry technique. After poor results in CCS pilot studies (e.g., Frio, Texas, USA), it has not been applied to commercial case projects to date.	Müller et al. (2007).
	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR).	The NMR wireline logging tool is designed to measure the response of hydrogen with the main purpose of detecting liquid filled porosity, permeability and the initial water saturation.	Reservoir characterisation and monitoring of changes in fluid-fill with multiple logs through time.	A single pass in the wellbore provides total and effective porosity, permeability, and fluid identification and characterisation.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Vertical profile along the wellbore, focusing mainly on the deep geosphere of the injection zone.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	NMR measurements are made independently of other logging outputs and are unbiased by formation water salinity or the rock matrix.	NMR does not directly detect presence of CO ₂ . The technique requires interpretation in conjunction with other tools to identify changes in fluid-fill over time.	100ks EUR.	Mature.	SLB (2006).

GEOCHEMICAL

SUB-CATEGORY	Monitoring tool, technology, or technique	Description of the application /data acquisition	Scope/special considerations for offshore Netherlands	What does the data inform about the site and what to do with the data	Domain	Monitoring purpose (containment/conformance)	Spatial coverage	Continuous or on-demand monitoring	Timing of deployment (pre-injection, injection, post-injection)	Advantages	Challenges	Cost range	Maturity/previous applications	References
NATURAL GAS AND ISOTOPIC TRACERS	Isotopic tracers ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) plus noble gas isotopes of Xe and Kr natural gas tracers.	Carbon and oxygen are isotopic (i.e., stable in one or more forms) and the injected CO_2 itself can serve as a tracer. Depending on how the industrial CO_2 has been captured, the stream may also contain noble gases as a byproduct of the capture process. The isotopic signature must be distinctly different from those found in the surrounding environment to be able to be used as a tracer.	Attribute monitoring. Natural tracers can be differentiated from natural/background sources of CO_2 . Especially useful if gas is detected on the seafloor, or near a wellbore or pockmark etc. Can help to identify the of the origin/source of the gas/fluid. For CO_2 hub developers accepting CO_2 from multiple customers/sources (factories or refineries etc.), it may be harder to use natural isotopic ratios to distinguish between individual stores.	The data provides information about the origin/source of the CO_2 and if unfamiliar CO_2 has come from the CO_2 storage operations or not. Useful for both operators and regulators if there is a dispute related to the origin of CO_2 detected outside the storage complex. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is the only tracer that been deployed on a commercial CCS project.	Geosphere through marine biosphere (based on the ability to sample different domains).	Containment.	Storage complex.	The natural tracers are incorporated continuously within the CO_2 stream, but measurements are on-demand.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection.	Completely natural, where nothing is added to avoid potential pollution of the offshore environment. May be able to improve quantitative models of residual trapping of ions. Low cost (possibly free) compared to artificial tracers. Tracers will move at the same speed as injected gas.	Multiple storage locations in the same region could be subject to similar isotopic ratios, which might effect the long term viability of the approach.	Difficult to estimate a cost range. Need to factor in offshore acquisition and analysis cost. Analysis cost can range significantly, depending on the lab and operators agreement. Lab costs likely ~100k USD, but this depends on the frequency of collection per sample (~2k-3k USD). Does not include shipping and analysis costs.	Mature.	Emberley et al. (2005). Risk et al. (2015).
	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$.	Carbon and oxygen are isotopic (i.e., stable in one or more forms) and the injected CO_2 itself can serve as a tracer. Depending on how the industrial CO_2 has been captured, the stream may also contain noble gases as a byproduct of the capture process. The isotopic signature must be distinctly different from those found in the surrounding environment to be able to be used as a tracer.	Attribute monitoring. Natural tracers can be differentiated from natural/background sources of CO_2 . Especially useful if gas is detected on the seafloor, or near a wellbore or pockmark etc. Can help to identify the of the origin/source of the gas/fluid. For CO_2 hub developers accepting CO_2 from multiple customers/sources (factories or refineries etc.), it may be harder to use natural isotopic ratios to distinguish between individual stores.	The data provides information about the origin/source of the CO_2 and if unfamiliar CO_2 has come from the CO_2 storage operations or not. Useful for both operators and regulators if there is a dispute related to the origin of CO_2 detected outside the storage complex. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is the only tracer that been deployed on a commercial CCS project.	Geosphere and marine biosphere.	Containment.	Storage complex and marine biosphere.	Only detected by on-demand sampling in monitoring wells or with marine biosphere sampling.	Injection and post-injection.	Completely natural, where nothing is added to avoid potential pollution of the offshore environment. May be able to improve quantitative models of residual trapping of ions. Low cost (possibly free) compared to artificial tracers. Tracers will move at the same speed as injected gas.	Must be sufficient distinction between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of injected CO_2 and baseline fluids/gases. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ within the CO_2 stream needs to be isotopically different from carbonate minerals in the formation or HCO_3^- in the brine.	Depends on sampling frequency and complexity.	Mature, where the Quest project located is using the inherent $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - CO_2 .	Roberts et al. (2017).
	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$.	Carbon and oxygen are isotopic (i.e., stable in one or more forms) and the injected CO_2 itself can serve as a tracer. Depending on how the industrial CO_2 has been captured, the stream may also contain noble gases as a byproduct of the capture process. The isotopic signature must be distinctly different from those found in the surrounding environment to be able to be used as a tracer.	Attribute monitoring. Natural tracers can be differentiated from natural/background sources of CO_2 . Especially useful if gas is detected on the seafloor, or near a wellbore or pockmark etc. Can help to identify the of the origin/source of the gas/fluid. For CO_2 hub developers accepting CO_2 from multiple customers/sources (factories or refineries etc.), it may be harder to use natural isotopic ratios to distinguish between individual stores.	The data provides information about the origin/source of the CO_2 and if unfamiliar CO_2 has come from the CO_2 storage operations or not. Useful for both operators and regulators if there is a dispute related to the origin of CO_2 detected outside the storage complex. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is the only tracer that been deployed on a commercial CCS project.	Geosphere and marine biosphere.	Containment.	Storage complex and marine biosphere.	Only detected by on-demand sampling in monitoring wells or with marine biosphere sampling.	Injection and post-injection.	Completely natural, where nothing is added to avoid potential pollution of the offshore environment. May be able to improve quantitative models of residual trapping of ions. Low cost (possibly free) compared to artificial tracers. Tracers will move at the same speed as injected gas.	Rapid equilibration of O isotopes within the CO_2 and formation water is a challenge, and in such cases may not be reliable tracers for CO_2 attribution.	Depends on sampling frequency and complexity.	Mature in environmental applications.	Flude et al. (2016). Roberts et al. (2017). Semo et al. (2016). Shevalier et al. (2014).
	Perfluorocarbons (PFCs).	An artificial tracer traditionally used in O&G and geothermal industries to provide reservoir connectivity and identify flow paths.	Attribute monitoring and fingerprinting injected CO_2 . If CO_2 is detected in the shallow geosphere or marine biosphere the technique can be used to determine if it is naturally occurring CO_2 or CO_2 that has leaked from the storage complex.	The data provides information about the origin/source of the CO_2 and if unfamiliar CO_2 has come from the CO_2 storage operations or not. Useful for both operators and regulators if there is a dispute related to the origin of CO_2 detected outside the storage complex. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is the only tracer that been deployed on a commercial CCS project.	Geosphere through marine biosphere.	Conformance.	Storage complex and marine biosphere.	Can either in be injected continuously or in batches and is only detected by on-demand sampling.	Injection and post-injection.	Low cost and added tracers are more reliable as they have a unique inert composition. Soluble in CO_2 and with a low atmospheric abundance. PFCs can be used to tag multiple baches of CO_2 because there are up to 6 different signature types.	GWP potential and a reputational risk with deployment. Major losses could occur during CO_2 phase changes. This will have to be taken into account in the design and modelling. Leaking CO_2 at the seafloor will not be in supercritical form. Also in depleted field settings, injection will likely occur in a gas phase until reservoir pressure has been sufficiently increased to accept CO_2 in a liquid or supercritical phase. Tends also to be adsorbed by clay minerals.	Difficult to estimate costs. Dependent on the quantity of the tracers injected, which is a function of the background values and the precision of available measurement approaches. Given the GWP, this technique is unlikely to be utilized in a commercial CO_2 storage project.	Mature, with the most-common tracers used in the O&G industry. PFCs used in the In Salah project to track and identify the source of CO_2 detected from legacy wellbores across the field.	Ringrose et al. (2013). Roberts et al. (2017).
	SF_6 (sulphur hexafluoride).	Traditionally used in the O&G and geothermal industry to provide information on reservoir connectivity and flow paths.	Characterisation of flow within the reservoir and comparison to predicted CO_2 migration.	The data provides information about the origin/source of the CO_2 and if unfamiliar CO_2 has come from the CO_2 storage operations or not. Useful for both operators and regulators if there is a dispute related to the origin of CO_2 detected outside the storage complex. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is the only tracer that been deployed on a commercial CCS project.	Geosphere through marine biosphere.	Conformance.	Storage complex and marine biosphere.	Can either in be injected continuously or in batches and is only detected by on-demand sampling.	All stages of the monitoring program.	Mature technology with demonstrated application.	SF_6 has aGWP ~23,500x that of CO_2 .	Difficult to estimate costs. Dependent on the quantity of the tracers injected, which is a function of the background values and the precision of available measurement approaches. Given the GWP, this technique is unlikely to be utilized in a commercial CO_2 storage project.	Mature O&G industry tracer. Applied in the Frio, Texas pilot, but not in any commercial CCS project to date.	Roberts et al. (2017).
Noble gas (Xe, Kr, He, Ar, and Ne).	Noble gases can be used to geochemically fingerprint injected CO_2 . Noble gas tracers are inert, do not react with CO_2 or the surrounding environment and typically travel a roughly the same speed as CO_2 . Tracers can be continuous injected, or injected in intermitted bursts. Certain noble gases have several isotopes, such as Xe ($^{129}\text{Xe}/^{136}\text{Xe}$ or $^{132}\text{Xe}/^{136}\text{Xe}$). Depending on how the industrial CO_2 has been captured, the stream may also contain noble gases as a byproduct of the capture process. The isotopic signature must be distinctly different from those found in the surrounding environment to be able to be used as a tracer.	Characterisation of flow within the reservoir and comparison to predicted CO_2 migration. It also can be used to trace CO_2 migration in other parts of the deep geosphere or detect leaked CO_2 outside the storage complex. Fingerprinted CO_2 helps to differentiate CO_2 from natural/background sources.	The data provides information about the origin/source of the CO_2 and if unfamiliar CO_2 has come from the CO_2 storage operations or not. Useful for both operators and regulators if there is a dispute related to the origin of CO_2 detected outside the storage complex. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is the only tracer that been deployed on a commercial CCS project.	Geosphere through marine biosphere.	Containment.	Storage complex, hydrosphere, biosphere.	Can either in be injected continuously or in batches and is only detected by on-demand sampling.	All stages of the monitoring program.	Inert gases, which are environmentally friendly. Xe has low background values in the offshore setting and as multiple isotopes.	He and Ar are costly. Current atmospheric Ar and Ne abundance is rising. He and Ar are not commercially available. Kr, He, Ar and Ne cannot tag multiple batches. Noble gasses might not move at the same rate as injected fluids.	Difficult to estimate cost range due to the additional cost of sampling offshore. Literature suggests the cost could be 1-1.7 USD/t, reaching totals in the 100k USD range.	Tracer technology mature, however, the use of adding noble gas has been limited to CCS pilot projects (e.g., CO_2 SINK and Kr in Otway by CO2CRC).	Weber et al. (2021).	

MARINE BIOSPHERE

SUB-CATEGORY	Monitoring tool, technology, or technique	Description of the application /data acquisition	Scope/special considerations for offshore Netherlands	What does the data inform about the site and what to do with the data	Domain	Monitoring purpose (containment/conformance)	Spatial coverage	Continuous or on-demand monitoring	Timing of deployment (pre-injection, injection, post-injection)	Advantages	Challenges	Cost range	Maturity/previous applications	References
WATER COLUMN PROFILER/CHEMICAL SENSING	Conductivity, temperature and depth (CTD) probe.	Small, autonomous data recorder designed to monitor conductivity, temperature and pressure for profiling water columns. Typically also record pH, redox, etc.	Leakage monitoring around legacy and injection wellbores or known faults. No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Leakage monitoring near a wellbore or a fault.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Local point of measurement.	Continuous.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Simple to deploy from a vessel. Can gather a wide range of geochemical measurements (pH, O ₂ , pCO ₂) depending on the sensor choice. Can also be deployed around well head.	Water currents may reduce the ability to detect subtle or very localized changes in geochemistry (e.g., pH signals). Instruments are often sensitive to other environmental parameters (e.g., temperature, salinity, currents and O ₂). Baseline measurements are important, but challenges lie in distinguishing injected CO ₂ leakage from natural variations which may occur at different concentrations, as well as temporal and spatial scales.	10ks EUR.	Mature and is planned to be deployed at the Goldeneye/Peterhead CCS project, offshore UK.	Wood Hole Oceanographic Institution (2023a).
WATER SAMPLING	Geochemical water column sampling.	Usually combined with CTD probe measurements.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Leakage monitoring near a wellbore or a fault.	Marine biosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Local point of measurement using a water sampling rosette. 12 x 10 L Niskin bottles are used for the Slepner project.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Can measure dissolved gas concentrations and inorganic carbon at selected depths and locations.	Water currents may reduce the ability to detect subtle or very localized changes in geochemistry (e.g., pH signals). Instruments are often sensitive to other environmental parameters (e.g., temperature, salinity, currents and O ₂). Baseline measurements are important, but challenges lie in distinguishing injected CO ₂ leakage from natural variations which may occur at different concentrations, as well as temporal and spatial scales.	10ks EUR.	Mature.	Wood Hole Oceanographic Institution (2023a).
WATER/SEDIMENT SAMPLING	Benthic chamber.	Measures fluxes of pCO ₂ and O ₂ across the sediment-water interface.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Impacts of leakage on seafloor flora and fauna.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Local point of measurement.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Simultaneous sediment and water sampling with easy deployment.	--	10ks EUR.	Mature.	Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology (2023).
	Multi-corer.	Sampling for chemical, geochemical, and biological applications.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Impacts of leakage on seafloor flora and fauna.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Spot samples at various depths.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Unique insight into the sediment water interface. Can take multiple samples (e.g., 4-12 cores) in sealed core barrels that preserve the sediment-water interface.	--	10ks EUR.	Mature.	Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology (2023).
	Van Veen grab samplers.	For collecting seabed flora and fauna (not living organisms).	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Impacts of leakage on seafloor flora and fauna.	Marine biosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Can extract samples >20 cm deep within a sampling area of 0.1 m ² .	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Simple to deploy from a vessel and are reliable corer tools, typically sampling an area of 0.1 m ² , but can be larger.	Depth of sediment penetration is shallow compared to coring techniques. Samples are not sealed, therefore, trapped gas can escape. Contamination is more common than with piston or gravity coring. Produces significant disturbances to sediment. Cannot sample overlying water and is not designed to collect living organisms.	10ks EUR.	Mature.	Wood Hole Oceanographic Institution (2023b).
	Piston corer.	A gravity-driven corer for penetrating the sediment water interface.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Impacts of leakage on seafloor flora and fauna.	Marine biosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Cores can be long (e.g., >18 m into the sediment).	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Can be long (e.g., >18 m), producing the most undisturbed samples (e.g., compared to vibrocorer) as the core barrel is not vibrated into the sediment.	Poor recovery in sandy sediments and cannot be used for pore pressure sampling.	100ks EUR.	Mature.	Wood Hole Oceanographic Institution (2023c).
	Vibrocorer.	Electrically powered corer, which vibrates a weight on top of the core barrel to force the corer into the sediment from the seafloor.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Impacts of leakage on seafloor flora and fauna.	Marine biosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Cores 1-5 m long.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Good sediment recovery in sandy sediments.	Collects one core at a time, increasing costs by using more time, and cannot be used for pore-pressure style samples.	100ks EUR.	Mature.	Aspect Land & Hydrographic Surveys (2023).
SEABED IMAGING	Video camera.	Detects and records high-definition images of bubbles and other features such as bacterial mats and fauna behaviors, which could give an indication of CO ₂ (natural or leaking).	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Impacts of leakage on seafloor flora and fauna.	Marine biosphere.	Containment and conformance.	Several meters.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Low cost.	Image quality can vary depending on water quality and depth (luminosity), and is a highly qualitative technique.	100ks EUR.	Mature.	IEAGHG (2015).
	Side-scan sonar (SSS).	Provides a high-resolution acoustic image of the seabed. Used to detect water column features (e.g., bubbles). Data can be mosaiced to produce seabed feature maps with accurate coordinates and at scale. Usually coupled with the MBES and SBP systems.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Leakage monitoring within a specified area.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Large areas of investigation.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Can be deployed from a mobile platform (survey vessel, USV, ROV or AUV).	Provides only a 2D image of the seafloor (no depth information). Detection of water-column objects is rather inconsistent. SSS data are prone to noise issues and therefore needs to be carefully interpreted by an experienced geoscientist. SSS mosaics/maps can be difficult to understand by non-experts and are prone to misinterpretation. Not as effective as MBES, exhibits poorer imaging range versus resolution and lacks the depth information provided by MBES.	1M EUR and usually coupled with MBES and SBP systems.	Mature.	Geoscience Australia (2023).
	Seafloor pressure gauges (pressure monitoring transducers [PMT]) (e.g., Fetch AZA from Sonadyrne).	Water depth measurement.	The Dutch sector of the southern North Sea hosts heavy marine traffic such as commercial shipping associated with the Port of Rotterdam, the fishing industry and wind farm construction and maintenance activities. Any sensors placed on the seafloor, would have to be protected from fishing net/trawler entanglement or ship anchors. Survey placement would have to be done in full cooperation with other parties in the marine setting. Exclusion zones may need to be considered if AMT are a key technology of a storage site.	Monitoring of the seafloor deformation, as well as potential CO ₂ migration or fault reactivation.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Local point of measurement.	Continuous (regular site visits to acquire pressure data).	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Self-calibrating, and can operate at depths of up to 6000 m. Data can be now be recovered using USVs.	Unlike MBES surveys, this technique only provides point-based depth data at instrument locations.	--	Mature.	Sonadyrne (2023b).

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	Acoustic monitoring transponders (AMT) (i.e., acoustic ranging).	Seafloor deformation monitoring with transponder instruments on the seafloor to measure horizontal strain/deformation associated with reservoir heave/subsidence (lateral and vertical movements). Stations pulse sound to neighbouring receiver stations. The accuracy is ~5-10 cm and repeatability in order of 1 cm. The direction and velocity of movement are measured, providing indications of plume movement (i.e., conformance or non-conformance). Measurements can be integrated with other monitoring data. Precise positions of AMTs come from acoustic GPS (GPS-A). Data retrieval can be wireless using unmanned surface vessels, such as Wave Gliders from Liquid Robotics. Using unmanned systems saves cost, as they typically have running costs that are one or two orders of magnitude lower than average manned vessels.	The Dutch sector of the southern North Sea hosts heavy marine traffic such as commercial shipping associated with the Port of Rotterdam, the fishing industry and wind farm construction and maintenance activities. Any sensors placed on the seafloor, would have to be protected from fishing net/trawler entanglement or ship anchors. Survey placement would have to be done in full cooperation with other parties in the marine setting. Exclusion zones may need to be considered if AMT are a key technology of a storage site.	CO ₂ pressure effect on the geosphere. Data best combined with down-hole pressure data, geophysical images and petrophysical data.	Geosphere.	Conformance.	Full-field coverage.	Continuous.	Pre-injection (baseline) and injection.	Effective way of monitoring pressure bowl effects.	Sufficient heave in the formation is required in order for the instruments to detect deformation. The technique also requires receivers to be placed on the seabed. If the seabed is extremely soft, the monitoring stations can sink.	Cost of transponders is ~2k EUR and ~100k EUR to install.	Mature and was used at the Ormen Lange gas field in the Norwegian Sea and the Jintan gas field in offshore Malaysia. It has also been deployed in the UK North Sea, Gulf of Mexico, and offshore Asia.	Dunn (2019). Sonardyne (2023a).
	Ground positioning system (GPS).	Helps detect ground movements, as fluids leaking from the seafloor around a platform or sub-sea template/well pad could be related to subsidence or uplift caused by injection.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Provides coordinates and location data for measurement.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Pointsource measurements (e.g., the platform or near wellheads).	Continuous.	Pre-injection, injection and post-injection.	Widely available and very accurate. If multiple stations are placed on a platform, 3D displacement can be mapped. Can achieve millimeter-scale resolution measurements in both horizontal and vertical directions.	Must have a fixed station location, and in the offshore setting, monitoring is limited to small areas (i.e., around infrastructure) and not the greater area of review.	10s EUR per station.	Mature.	--
	Acoustic cameras (echoscope) sonar.	Real time 3D imaging sonar.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Helps detect acoustic irregularities and possible leakage.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Large areas of investigation.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline) and injection.	All water conditions including low- or zero-visibility conditions.	Not as effective as MBES, with poorer imaging range versus image resolution, and lacks the depth information provided by MBES. Also may difficult to detect bubbles because of resolution.	--	Mature.	IEAGHG (2015).
SEABED IMAGING/ LEAK DETECTION	Multibeam echo sounder (MBES).	Assists in bubble leak detection, where MBES provides water depth data that can be processed and provide a geographically referenced DTM of the seabed. The resolution of the DTM is mainly governed by the operating frequency of the MBES and the height of the water column through which the acoustic pulse must travel, therefore high-frequency/small water column equates to a high-resolution DTM and vice versa. For the highest resolution DTM, an MBES system should account for the expected water column height and consider that high frequencies are attenuated quickly in water. MBES processing to produce a DTM involves conditioning of the raw dataset to remove spurious data points, such as those scattered by features within the water column. Gas bubbles in the water column can be detected by a high-frequency MBES, however the data must be processed sufficiently to preserve these data points.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Leakage monitoring within a specified area.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Large areas of investigation.	On-demand.	Pre-injection (baseline), injection and post-injection.	Can image seafloor and water column, which is key for bubble detection. Fully developed technology, well understood. High-accuracy/resolution data.	Must perform a cost-benefit analysis to validate use.	1M EUR and usually coupled with SSS and SBP systems.	Mature.	IEAGHG (2015). Leighton and White (2011).
	Active acoustic synthetic aperture sonar (SAS).	High-resolution sonar, which combines a number of acoustic pings during the continuous movement of the host platform (e.g., boat) to synthesize a longer sonar array than conventional methods such as side-scan sonar which in comparison requires less battery power.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	High-resolution seafloor imagery and bathymetry makes it possible to detect fluid-escape features such as pockmarks, bacterial mats, etc.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Large survey areas (1-2 km ² /h).	On-demand.	Injection and post-injection.	Large survey areas.	Greater power requirements compared to SSS.	--	Mature.	Waarum et al. (2017).
LEAK DETECTION	Passive acoustic sensors.	Bubble leakage detection, where characteristic sounds emitted by bubbles in the water column are measured. These include the sound emitted as a bubble enters the water column from the sediment-water interface, the sound caused by the oscillations of a gas-filled bubble within the water column, and the high-frequency sound caused by a bubble as it bursts. Passive acoustic sensors (hydrophones) are able to measure these sounds, but the acoustic signal power is the power emitted from the bubbles alone, which is generally much lower than what is achievable using active acoustic systems.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting, however, can't be deployed in busy areas (lots of background noise).	Leakage monitoring near a wellbore or a fault.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Local point of measurement.	On-demand.	Injection and post-injection.	Passive acoustic sensors are robust and energy-efficient methodology.	Background noise within the marine environment issue (e.g., instrument noise from itself or other instruments in the vicinity). In the case of a leakage from a pressurized pipeline, the flux is normally large and focused, giving rise to a strong acoustic signal. Hence, passive acoustic sensors detect leakage from significant changes in the acoustic field. For monitoring of a CO ₂ storage site, the area coverage rate may need to be larger, and the expected location of potential leakage may not necessarily be well-defined. For this application, highly sensitive sensors and advanced processing may be required to identify leakage and to differentiate between leakage and background noise (e.g., ships, operation activity, animals, breaking waves, currents, wind farms, rainfall, etc.). Relevant methods include use of directional sensors, and mounting of several sensors in an array configuration that allows more accurate positioning of leakage zones, as well as improved signal-to-noise ratio.	Low cost.	Mature.	Leighton and White (2011).

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	Sentry integrity monitoring sonar.	Bubble leakage detection.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	Leakage monitoring near a wellbore or a fault.	Marine biosphere.	Containment.	Provides 360°, high-volume coverage from a single location and is sensitive to small leaks within a 500 m radius.	On-demand.	Injection and post-injection.	Generates near real-time automatic alerts of any seeps detected in the water column. Sentry sonar head, which is mounted on a seafloor lander, is connected into an existing power and communication umbilical to a floating facility. Capable of monitoring more than 1B ft ³ (~28.2M m ³) of seawater, with 360° of coverage from a single sonar sensor location. Automation reduces the need for automatic supervision. Associated with a low false-alarm rate.	In testing.	--	Deployed and in testing.	Sonardyne (2023c, d).
	Ocean acoustic wave-guide remote sensing (OAWRS).	To realistically model CO ₂ emissions (for quantification and impact assessments) in the marine environment, site-specific current data are needed. An acoustic doppler current profiler measures ocean currents using the principle of doppler shifts. It emits a series of high-frequency pulses of sound that bounce off moving particles in the water. If the particle is moving away from the instrument, the returned signal is at a lower frequency and vice versa. Because the particles move at the same speed as the water that carries them, the speed of the water current can be determined.	No special considerations for the Dutch southern North Sea setting.	An acoustic doppler current profiler measures ocean currents and needs to be used in combination with other monitoring techniques for more detailed analysis.	Marine biosphere.	Containment (in combination with other techniques).	Typically deployed on a fixed-surface structure/buoy pointing downwards or on a seafloor structure/lander pointing upwards. Data can be collected through the water column, giving current speed and direction in a number of 'depth buckets' throughout the water column.	On-demand.	Injection and post-injection.	Long-term and long-distance measurements are possible. OAWRS may be suitable for first-pass surveying of a storage site and perhaps capable of detecting major leaks of a significant areal extent.	May have limitations on depth of deployment due to low-resolution.	--	Mature.	National Ocean Service (2023).

INNOVATIVE

TOOL, TECHNOLOGY, OR TECHNIQUE	Potential applications	Domain	Timing	Advantages	Challenges	References/notes
CASING INSPECTION TOOLS	Casing inspection tools are used to assess the condition of the well casings, which is part of the integrity barrier envelope of a well ensuring there are no leaks into the environment.	Wells.	Several tools are already available and improvements are regularly made to existing tools.	Early detection of casing integrity issues. Enhanced safety and environmental protection. Provides monitoring of well integrity over time and allows for data-driven decision-making.	Inspection tools require full wellbore access for the casing to be inspected effectively. Inspection of outer casings is generally not possible with the required detail. There is potential for false readings or misinterpretation, and the technique relies on accurate interpretation of the collected data. Although tools are effective in detecting many casing integrity issues, they have limitations in detecting certain types of defects, such as microfractures or internal corrosion.	SLB (2004b). Spartek Systems (2023a).
VIRTUAL FLOW METERS	Calculates flow rate from compressor to reservoir using existing sensors from the system, such as pressures and temperatures combined with diameters and detailed fluid phase data.	Wells and pipelines.	Work continues toward improving fluid handling by the software, but could be commercial by 2025.	Virtual flow meters eliminate the need for physical hardware and are cost-effective. Systems run on computers and only requires connections with sensor data. Virtual meters can be scaled and adapted to different injection systems. Meters provide real-time monitoring and analysis. Easy integration with existing monitoring systems, as it can share computer data.	Meter rely on mathematical algorithms and models to estimate flow rates based on available processed data. Depend heavily on the availability and quality of input data, such as pressure, temperature and composition. Must be calibrated and validated using physical flow meter measurements or other reference methods to ensure accuracy. Tools are vulnerable to software issues. Unlike physical flow meters, virtual flow meters do not offer a redundant physical device (control) for measurement.	Turbulent Flux (2020).
AUTONOMOUS SEISMIC SURVEY SUB-SEA NODES, BLUE OCEAN SEISMIC NODES (BOSS) OR FLYING NODES	Fully autonomous, self-repositioning nodes using swarm technologies.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Commercial by 2024.	Has a significantly lower carbon footprint and environmental impact, providing a massive reduction in survey time and cost.	New technology, and possibly more suitable for more expensive, deepwater settings.	Blue Ocean Seismic Services (2023).
CO2M	CO ₂ monitoring from satellites.	Atmosphere (satellite).	Satellites planned to be launched in 2026.	Remote, autonomous, and broad.	Low-resolution.	European Space Agency (2021).
REAL-TIME CASING IMAGING (RTC)	Measures 3D casing deformations to infer reservoir compaction and extension. Changes in travel time (of light) is measured through [multiple] fibre-optic cable(s) wrapped around the casing and along complex deformed features requiring interpretation.	Wells.	Allows real-time monitoring of reservoir decompaction via fibre-optic cables wrapped around the casing for assessing effects of CO ₂ injection on cement integrity. The first real-time casing imaging tool was developed in the early 1990s by GeoPilot, but is now held by Baker Hughes and named the 'CasingView' tool.	Fibre-optic cables can provide precise and accurate measurements of casing deformations and have the capability to detect small changes in strain or displacement, allowing for detailed analysis of the casing behavior under various conditions. Enable continuous monitoring of casing deformations over time. Has 3D measurement capability using multiple fibre-optic cables wrapped around the casing, capturing 3D casing deformations. Fibre-optic sensing systems can provide real-time data acquisition, allowing for immediate feedback on casing deformations. Known for durability and resistance to harsh environments.	Installation of multiple fiber-optic cables wrapped around the casing can be a complex and time-consuming process, and requires careful planning and expertise. Implementing a fiber-optic sensing system for measuring 3D casing deformations can involve significant upfront costs. Analyzing the data collected from fiber-optic sensors may require advanced data processing techniques and expertise. The accuracy and coverage of fiber-optic sensing systems may be influenced by factors such as cable length, number of sampling points, and signal attenuation. While fibre-optic cables are durable, they can still be susceptible to physical damage during well operations or interventions.	Halliburton (2020). Rambow et al. (2010). SLB (2021).
GLASS FIBRE-OPTIC TECHNIQUES	Glass fiber optics are being developed as a replacement for metal or plastic with positive initial results in data transfer applications.	Wells.	--	Faster transmission of data, and applicable in corrosive environments.	More fragile than metal wire systems.	--
SPOTLIGHT TECHNIQUES	Seismic technique that provides a low-cost traffic light type result.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Currently being tested in the Greensand project, Denmark.	Low cost, 'spot seismic' technique.	Non-comprehensive, and intended to flag the need for a full-field evaluation.	SpotLight (2023).
MUON TOMOGRAPHY	Measuring cosmic ray muon helps to monitor changes in the mean bulk density of storage layers, where detectors could be deployed in wells.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	--	Passive monitoring that is cheaper than 4D seismic.	--	Kudryavtsev et al. (2012).
NORTH SEA POSTHOLE INSTRUMENTS	Continuous and real-time seismic monitoring.	Shallow through deep geosphere.	Testing in 2023 and 2024, and available in 2025.	Is buried in the shallow sediments along the seafloor to be resistant to sand dynamics and have fewer issues related to tilting. The instrument is connected to a buoy for power sourced from batteries and solar panels. Instruments take advantage of the 4G networks over the North Sea for real-time data streaming. Integration into cross-North Sea seismic network is possible, and has accurate timing via GPS.	Not yet tested in the deeper North Sea around 25 m water depth. Seismic noise might still be significant near the seafloor.	Developed under the DICTUM research project funded by Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek (NWO) through the DeepNL program.